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D3.2 Multidimensional and Multi-Level Cross-Country Comparative Analysis of Key Thematic Areas

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
REA	European Research Executive Agency
WP	Work Package
MSF	Multiple Streams Framework
CFA	Critical Frame Analysis
DNA	Discourse Network Analysis
NGO	Non-governmental organization

Executive Summary

This report presents a multidimensional, cross-country comparative analysis of how feminist and anti-gender mobilizations influence policymaking on gender-related issues in eight European countries: Italy, Denmark, France, Greece, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and Turkey. It constitutes the core comparative output of WP3 within the FIERCE project and focuses on five key thematic areas: (1) LGBTIQ+ rights; (2) gender-based violence; (3) health and reproductive rights; (4) labour market, migration, and care; and (5) intersectionality. Drawing on data from interviews, critical frame analysis (CFA), and discourse network analysis (DNA), the report examines whether and how feminist and gendered policy frames gain political traction; which frames dominate public and policy debates; and under what conditions gender-related concerns are elevated, sidelined, or blocked in the policymaking process.

Analytically grounded in the Multiple Streams Framework (MSF) and framing theory, the report interrogates how gender issues are framed as public problems, what policy solutions are proposed or resisted, and how political climates enable or constrain change. Particular attention is given to the mechanisms through which gender issues enter the political agenda and the role of policy entrepreneurs, strategic framing, and actor alliances in the creation of windows of opportunity for policy change. It also highlights the interplay between local, national, and transnational dynamics, tracing how actors' discursive and strategic repertoires intersect with institutional opportunity structures.

This analysis aims to uncover broader patterns, tensions, and variations in how feminist movements advance gender equality, and how anti-gender forces contest or even reverse progress. By mapping both successful policy shifts and persistent blockages, the report offers new insight into the conditions under which gender issues influence, or fail to influence, contemporary democratic policymaking.

1. Introduction to the FIERCE Project

1.1. The FIERCE Project – Summary

FIERCE aims to provide theoretical and practical knowledge and tools to revitalize alliances between the feminist movement, civil society and political decision makers in a context of growing social inequalities, political disaffection and strengthening of populist radical right anti-gender/anti-feminist actors and discourses. The research has adopted an interdisciplinary, multi-dimensional and multi-level framework, that aimed to bridge the gaps that often arise from relying solely on narrowly defined disciplinary perspectives or nation-centred methodologies and approaches. FIERCE has developed in-depth understanding of feminist and anti-gender/anti-feminist movements, activities and discourses, and their impact on the institutional arena and on policy outcomes, focusing on the period 2010-2023. These actors, and especially the feminist movement, are studied through critical frame analysis, interviews and discourse network analysis. In each of these cases, the research paid special attention to key gender debates and controversies, prefigured to be situated in the following areas: LGBTIQ+ rights; gender-based violence; health and reproductive rights; labour market; and migration. FIERCE covers eight case studies – France, Italy, Greece, Slovenia, Turkey, Denmark, Poland, Spain – representing a wide variety of country contexts in socio-political, geographical and welfare terms. FIERCE strives to move beyond a country-based approach, to provide a cross-cutting comparative analysis of the way in which debates and controversies on gender have developed and influenced the dynamics and output of the policy processes. Building on co-creation methods and on a strong alliance with civil society organizations, the FIERCE proposed pilot actions aim at reinvigorating democratic practices, in line with feminist inclusive visions for the future of democracy. FIERCE thereby sets out a bottom-up, problem-driven and impact-oriented approach, bridging academic knowledge, policymaking, and bottom-up democratic strategies.

1.2. Description of WP3 and interconnections

The aim of WP3 is to move beyond the country-specific approach toward a comparative, multi-dimensional perspective focused on issue-driven policy processes. WP3 identifies, selects, and clusters core gender issues and dynamics across countries, thereby enabling the detection of shared analytical dimensions. This foundation is meant to support a cross-country comparative analysis within the project's five thematic areas: LGBTIQ+ rights; gender-based violence; health and reproductive rights; labour market; and migration.

WP3 adopts a multi-step approach to: (1) analyse how different policy contexts shaped agenda-setting, alliances, proposals, and decisions concerning gender-related issues; (2) identify new or unforeseen emerging issues that require attention; and (3) highlight overlapping dynamics that cut across thematic areas.

The work package builds on insights and data earlier generated in WP1, WP2, WP4, and WP5, providing a comprehensive framework for understanding gender issues in policymaking. Particularly, it draws on the rich pool of data gathered within the FIERCE project as well as reports, including: 1) critical frame analysis (CFA) applied to selected social movement documents and parliamentary debates; 2) semi-structured interviews with representatives of groups and organizations, activists, advocates, and politicians; and 3) discourse network analysis (DNA) of gender/anti-gender debates, levels of controversies, agreement/disagreement in actor positionings.

Additionally, WP3 incorporates findings from WP4's co-creative methodology, involving national and transnational collaborations through the so-called FIERCE Labs. These activities fostered knowledge exchange and yield empirical data on feminist strategies, democratic initiatives, and the development of inclusive tools and policy recommendations. The FIERCE actions, selected and accomplished within WP4, also provided empirical data for the analysis of feminist processes of democratic innovation (see D3.3) and intersectional alternatives for inclusion, participation, and empowerment.

WP3 is structured around three interconnected steps. The first step sets up the framework for the cross-country analysis. The theoretical and methodological approach to this task is informed by the Multi-Streams Framework (MSF) (see Kingdon, 1995; Zahariadis, 2014; 2015), the theory of Agenda Denial (Cobb & Ross, 1997) and Framing Theory (Bacchi, 1999; 2005; 2009; Benford, 1993; Benford & Snow 2000; Verloo, 2007). In addition to utilizing MSF and framing theory, this overall framework takes into account the role of emotions in political processes, acknowledging with this that such processes are shaped not only by normative and performative dynamics and relationships, but also by affective and emotional elements (e.g., Hochschild, 2014; 2016; Maor, 2024; Redlawsk, 2006; Widmann, 2021).

The second step moves towards the multidimensional and multi-level cross-country comparative analysis of the FIERCE key thematic areas. This constitutes the core of the comparative component of WP3, and it is the focus of this report. It examines whether and how feminist and gendered policy frames gain – or fail to gain – political traction across the country cases and particularly what issues and frames dominate the debate within the thematic areas. Particular attention is given to the mechanisms through which gender issues enter the political landscape, as well as to the factors that lead to political attention, silencing, or neglect. The scope is to explain under what conditions specific feminist and gendered policy frames succeed in reaching the political agenda, and eventually generate policy change – or, conversely, why some issues are ignored, or marginalized (Cobb & Ross, 1997, pp. 25-45). To do so, the analysis builds on empirical material gathered within WP1 and WP2, particularly through interviews, CFA and DNA, to investigate how feminist and anti-gender/anti-feminist actors articulate main frames and employ various discursive and strategic repertoires to advance, or block gender-related concerns and disputes, and how these efforts are shaped by political and societal contexts. It further explores how the interaction between local, national, regional, and transnational actors and alliances influences opportunities for institutional engagement, inclusion, or exclusion.

The final step takes stock of the cross-country comparative analysis of feminist innovations to rekindle democratic processes. It examines feminist democratic innovations in a comparative context (see deliverable 3.3). It maps how feminist movements contribute to revitalizing democratic processes and evaluates the strategies, tools, and practices they employ and the limits they face to promote more inclusive and participatory governance.

By linking these different steps (see in the GA T3.1., T3.2, T3.3) under WP3, we systematically unpack the dynamics of gendered policymaking (across countries and thematic areas), their intersections, and the potential for feminist-driven democratic transformation.

2. Multidimensional and Multi-Level Cross-Country Comparative Analysis of Key Thematic Areas

2.1. Introduction

Over the past decade, feminist and LGBTIQ+ movements in Europe and beyond have faced ongoing challenges from anti-gender/anti-feminist mobilizations aimed at restricting equality politics (Kuhar &

Paternotte, 2017; Verloo, 2018a). These mobilizations bring together a diverse network of actors, including religious organizations, “pro-life” groups, far-right political parties and movements, and self-identified “concerned citizens” – many of which maintain close ties with, or operate in alignment with religious institutions and ultraconservative think-tanks (Datta, 2025). While varying in form and emphasis, they often share a critical stance toward feminist advancements and advocate for more conservative understandings of family, kinship, sexuality, and intimate citizenship more broadly (Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017, p. 4).

The anti-gender movement gained significant traction in public discourse by the mid-2000s, particularly around debates on marriage equality, which served as a catalyst for national and transnational mobilizations (e.g., *La Manif pour Tous*). However, its political ambitions extend well beyond opposition to LGBTIQ+ rights and encompass efforts to restrict sexual and reproductive rights, sex education in public schools, the rights of transgender persons, sexual liberalism, knowledge production, and the very concept of gender itself (Korolczuk, 2023).

Research highlights the explicitly transnational nature of this movement (Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017; Lavizzari & Siročić, 2023), evident in its coordinated strategies, shared discursive patterns, and similar repertoires of action, ranging from lobbying and protest organization to media campaigns, fundraising, and exerting political influence on legislative processes (Caiani & Tranfić, 2024; Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017). Moreover, strategic alliances with far-right political actors in power have become pivotal to the successful implementation of anti-gender/anti-feminist agendas at the policy level (Caravantes, Elizondo & Lombardo, 2024; Kantola & Lombardo, 2024). Lavizzari (2025) defines the relationship between anti-gender actors and far-right political actors as “symbiotic”, emphasizing how anti-gender practices have become integrated into mainstream political processes. Their growing impact on policymaking has become particularly visible in several national contexts, as also evidenced by the edited volume resulting from the FIERCE project (Smrdelj & Kuhar, 2025). In Poland, anti-gender actors have played a central role in pushing for increasingly restrictive abortion laws (Muszel, 2025). In Slovenia, they successfully mobilized support for two national referenda, significantly delaying the implementation of marriage equality legislation (Markelj & Pajnik, 2025). In Greece, they managed to reform the Family Law, enacting the “mandatory shared custody” of the children of divorced couples, which forces victims of abuse to maintain close contact with abusers (Kioupkiolis, 2025a; Kioupkiolis & Grammatikopoulou, 2025). In Turkey, anti-gender mobilizations were instrumental in the government’s decision to withdraw from the Istanbul Convention (Alniaçık & Altan-Olcay, 2025). Most recently, in Hungary, such actors have supported and reinforced a legislative crackdown targeting LGBTIQ+ rights.

However, democratic backsliding should not be seen merely as the formal repeal or dismantling of gender equality policies, but also as a more gradual and often subtle reframing of gender-related issues (Krizsan & Roggeband, 2018a, p. 97). The objective of anti-gender movements is not only to weaken existing progressive legislation, but to construct an alternative anti-gender narrative and project through which they seek to establish a “cultural hegemony” (Lombardo, 2024; Verloo & Paternotte, 2018). In this process, feminist knowledge is frequently portrayed as ideological, or lacking scientific legitimacy, and gender equality is targeted through the dissemination of misleading or distorted information.

Crucially, these processes are closely intertwined with the normalization of far-right agendas and discourses (Krzyżanowski et al., 2023; Wodak, 2022), which contributed to shifting the boundaries of what is considered acceptable in political and public discourse. Normalization expands normative boundaries, diminishes the perceived severity of deviations from democratic norms, and naturalizes ideologies that previously lay outside of mainstream common sense (Krzyżanowski, 2020). By integrating right-wing

ideas into the political and policy mainstream, this shift reshapes public domains in ways that legitimize untruthfulness and exclusionary rhetoric (Wodak, 2015; 2022). As Wodak warns (2022, p. 799), such developments pave the way for the incremental implementation of authoritarian tendencies within liberal democracies. In this context, normalization is not merely a discursive shift, but a broader political and policy process that legitimizes populist and exclusionary ideologies while undermining democratic values and feminist gains.

At the same time, we have witnessed a resurgence of feminist mobilizations since the 2000s, emerging in response to rapidly shifting social, political, and economic conditions, as documented in our second edited volume based on FIERCE research (Bonu Rosenkranz & della Porta, 2025a). This renewed activism has taken shape against the backdrop of economic crises, austerity measures, the rise of right-wing politics, and an intensifying backlash against feminist achievements (Dean & Aune, 2015), most notably exemplified by the proliferation of anti-gender/anti-feminist movements. In the last decade, a new cycle of transnational feminist mobilizations and protests took shape in Europe. While countries such as Poland, Turkey, Spain, Greece, and Italy have been particularly influenced by the international feminist strike from Latin America, other contexts, where the impact of transnational mobilization has traditionally been more limited, such as Slovenia and Denmark, have nonetheless experienced a notable revitalization of feminist activism (della Porta & Bonu Rosenkranz, 2025, p. 13). In these cases, mobilizations have been spurred less by direct transnational diffusion and more by domestic triggers, including reactionary political shifts, the rise of anti-gender initiatives, and concrete threats to gender equality, which have prompted new alliances and public contestation.

In many countries, feminist critiques of gender regimes are increasingly interwoven with critiques of neoliberal capitalism, as contemporary feminist movements have consolidated an intersectional framework, increasingly building alliances with other progressive movements (della Porta & Bonu Rosenkranz, 2025). This marks a shift from essentialist and unitary understandings of feminist identity toward coalition-based intersectional approaches. Following Yuval-Davis (2006), “transversality” has become a key principle in organizing collective action, enabling the articulation of diverse positionalities around shared struggles. Building on this, Anthias (2012) emphasizes the importance of “translocational positionality” for understanding how social actors navigate intersecting axes of power and identity across different contexts, offering a framework for coalition-building that moves beyond fixed categories. Understanding social categories as relational and context-dependent enables the formation of solidarities that are reflexive and attentive to internal power dynamics and exclusions. Intersectional and transversal coalitions shaped by these approaches have gained increasing visibility, particularly around issues such as reproductive rights, equal pay, care work, and gender-based violence (Bereni, 2021; Dean & Aune, 2015).

The repertoires of feminist action have also evolved, with notable innovations in organizing practices, including feminist strikes, performances, creative legal activism, and direct social action (Altan-Olcay & Alnıçık, 2025; Bonu Rosenkranz & della Porta, 2025b; Jourde, 2025; Markelj & Pajnik, 2025). The use of digital platforms has facilitated the emergence of transnational feminist networks (Altan-Olcay & Alnıçık, 2025; Bonu Rosenkranz & della Porta, 2025b; Gregersen, Augustín & Meret, 2025; Jourde, 2025; Kioupiolis, 2025b; Muszel & Piotrowski, 2025), as evidenced by campaigns such as #MeToo, which helped reframe sexual violence as a systemic and global issue. Together, these developments have expanded the scale, visibility, and impact of feminist mobilizations, fostering new forms of solidarity across borders and contexts.

Feminist mobilizations have not only broadened political participation but have also succeeded in bringing feminist issues into the centre of legislative and policy agendas across Europe. While these feminist

endeavours often appear as reactive responses to the rise of anti-gender mobilizations, they also reflect autonomy and continuity within EU policymaking. These efforts build upon a decade-long institutionalization of gender equality policies and gender mainstreaming, which has promoted the systematic integration of gender perspectives across various policy fields. As emphasized by Abels et al. (2021), the EU's commitment to gender mainstreaming has shaped the procedural and discursive conditions under which gender issues can be addressed today. This historical foundation helps explain not only the resilience of feminist actors in the face of backlash but also their capacity to advance new, innovative and proactive strategies that push the boundaries of inclusion within existing institutional frameworks. A particularly noteworthy example of transnational feminist engagement is the 2024 "My Voice, My Choice" campaign, a pan-European initiative aimed at safeguarding abortion rights, which brought together more than 300 feminist organizations across Europe (My Voice, My Choice, n.d.). This campaign adopts participatory democratic tools (European Citizens' Initiative) that enable EU citizens to directly shape policy at the European level and indicates the capacity of feminist movements to organize transnationally. In recent years, feminist advocacy has contributed to several significant policy achievements advancing gender equality in various national contexts. In Slovenia, reforms have eliminated discrimination based on marital status and sexual orientation in access to assisted reproductive technologies, and same-sex marriage and adoption rights have been legalized (Markelj & Pajnik, 2025). Similarly, in France the "Medically Assisted Procreation for All", adopted in 2021, remedied discrimination in accessing reproductive technologies to lesbian couples and single mothers. Denmark, Slovenia, and Spain have adopted legal reforms redefining sexual violence and rape based on the principle of affirmative consent through "Only Yes Means Yes" laws (Campillo et al., 2025; Gregersen, Augustín & Meret, 2025; Markelj & Pajnik, 2025). Notably, France has enshrined abortion rights in its constitution, thanks to an efficient convergence between feminist political representatives and feminist movements, using the window of opportunity opened by the setbacks on abortion rights in the US. In Italy, recent legislative developments have introduced femicide as a distinct category in criminal law. These policy achievements demonstrate the concrete outcomes of civil society mobilisations and the strength of transversal and transnational alliances. Even in cases where there has been attempts to regress existing rights, the presence of vocal feminist movements has either prevented them, slowed them down or created the conditions under which regressions created expanding public outcry. The resilience of feminist mobilization even under inauspicious circumstances should be emphasized (Alınışık & Altan-Olcay, 2025). These examples also help counterbalance the tendency in scholarly research to focus on the backsliding and erosion of existing rights, highlighting instead the diverse, non-linear, and often contradictory trajectories of the policy processes.

Feminist movements across Europe have increasingly transitioned from reactive or defensive responses, to proactive, strategic, and deliberate forms of "productive resistance" (Srnđelj & Kuhar, 2025). This entails the access to a spectrum of developed strategies and tactics ranging from confrontational public actions to institutional strategies such as counter-framing, litigation, and parliamentary engagement to resist delegitimization, counter misinformation, and confront anti-gender backlash (Cullen, 2021; Caravantes, Elizondo & Lombardo, 2024). Feminist movements have historically been innovative, entrepreneurial and proactive in character, leading struggles for emancipation, recognition and expansion of gender-related rights. Their current mobilizations, while in part responding to the rise of anti-gender mobilizations, also continue within this tradition of rights expansion and democratic innovation. Nevertheless, the growing influence of anti-gender movements, also in economic support (Datta, 2021; 2025), continues to constrain their political impact, presenting an escalating threat to democratic institutions and principles. Despite these developments, the political processes, mechanisms, and actors'/entrepreneurs' interactions that drive policy change in gender-sensitive domains have rarely been examined

through a genuine comparative (policy process) lens, across national contexts and policy areas. In light of this gap, a more systematic comparative perspective is needed to understand how feminist and anti-gender mobilizations interact with institutional configurations, political opportunity structures, and shifting societal conditions to influence policymaking. This report strives to contribute to that effort, by investigating how these antagonistic political forces shape some of the most pressing challenges to contemporary democracy, particularly with regard to policy outcomes and institutional change. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions: *What influences the inclusion or exclusion of gender-related issues on political agendas, and how do feminist mobilizations contribute to generate impact (discursive, policy, and/or legal change) across the diverse contexts? What deeper insights on dynamics of influence can be gained by adopting a comparative approach to the analysis of gender-related issues within policy processes?*

As policy change arises from a dynamic and complex interaction of actors, strategies, alliances, and shifting societal and political conditions, shaped by evolving agendas and institutional priorities, key inquiries within this comparative framework include why certain policy issues and problem framings gain traction, how they are elevated onto political agendas, and what roles are played by various actors (such as political leaders and entrepreneurs, civil society movements and advocates, and the media) in shaping these trajectories. Understanding which policy solutions are proposed, how they gain support or encounter resistance, and what leads to their adoption or rejection is fundamental to analysing the contemporary struggles over democracy and equality.

Within the context of the FIERCE project, where gender and gender-related policies have been central concerns, it is particularly important to unpack the underlying factors, conditions, and mechanisms that facilitate, or hinder, policy change. Equally crucial is the study of actors – their relationships, behaviours, and strategic choices – which ultimately determine whether specific gender issues become public and policy priorities or end up being marginalized and excluded from formal agendas or are negatively targeted by decision-makers. In the case of social movements, this also requires consideration of whether these seek to engage with institutional politics or abstain from it, and the contextual motivations behind such deliberations.

Building on this approach, this report presents an analysis of the policy processes surrounding the most salient gender-related issues and core debates across the eight country cases: Italy, Denmark, France, Greece, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and Turkey, building on the empirical data from interviews, CFA and DNA. It focuses on the project's key thematic areas: (1) LGBTIQ+ rights; (2) gender-based violence; (3) health and reproductive rights; (4) labour market, migration, and care; and (5) intersectionality – the latter emerging inductively as a cross-cutting and increasingly central perspective in policy debates throughout the countries under study. Although migration was initially identified as one of the key thematic areas of the project, it is not addressed as a standalone domain in this report. Instead, migration emerges as a cross-cutting issue that intersects with care issues and with some of the five primary thematic areas, such as labour market, gender-based violence and reproductive rights. It is also considered as part of the broader socio-political context in which feminist and anti-gender mobilizations unfold, influencing both the content and framing of policy debates, and the dynamics of political engagement.

In the following sections of the report, we first outline the theoretical background, drawing on the Multiple Streams Framework (MSF) and framing theory. These approaches enable us to identify and conceptualize discursive and strategic repertoires of the anti-gender and feminist movements, as well as key factors underlying policy processes, drawing on the empirical material derived from the three FIERCE research streams (interviews, CFA and DNA). Each of these streams and methods are discussed in the subsequent methodological section, along with the rationale behind our comparative analytical

approach. We then present our findings across the five thematic areas, examining how the articulation of policy frames and the strategic deployment of repertoires of action by feminist and anti-gender actors shape both opportunities and constraints for agenda-setting and policy reform across varying political and societal contexts. In this section, we explore the continuum of policymaking, highlighting both direct policy outcomes and the indirect influence exerted through agenda-setting and strategic framing. In the discussion, we address the crosscutting patterns and key findings of the analyses conducted across themes and countries and we highlight how MSF and framing theory are integrated throughout the analysis to provide nuanced findings regarding the dynamics of gender-related agenda-setting and policymaking in Europe.

2.2. Theoretical Background¹

This section outlines the theoretical foundations that inform our comparative analysis of how anti-gender and feminist actors construct frames and deploy discursive and strategic repertoires to engage with institutional and political contexts and influence policymaking. Central to our analysis are two epistemological approaches, which serve both as theoretical foundations and analytical frameworks. The first is the Multiple Streams Framework (MSF), which offers tools for examining how policy windows open and close, and how actors, problem frames, strategies, and political contexts converge to shape policy outcomes. Through this lens, we investigate the conditions, similarities, and differences that have enabled, or hindered, policy impacts across diverse national settings. Complementing this, we draw on framing theory which allows us to explore how political and social issues are discursively constructed, revealing how problems and solutions are framed, whose voices are privileged or silenced, and how frames shift across institutional contexts.

From both theoretical and methodological perspectives, these two frameworks enable a comparative, dimension-driven analysis of gender-related policymaking, highlighting the strategic discursive practices and policy developments through which feminist and anti-gender actors seek influence, navigate constraints, establish alliances, and contest power relations.

2.2.1. The Multiple Streams Framework

The Multiple Streams Framework (MSF) was originally developed by John Kingdon (1984) in his book *Agendas, Alternatives, and Public Policies*. It is a theory that has reached quite some scholarly popularity over the years (see Béland & Howlett, 2016) for understanding and explaining policymaking “under conditions of ambiguity, or situations when there is more than one way of thinking about the same problem” (DeLeo, Zohlnhöfer & Zahariadis, 2024, p. 1). MSF conceptualizes policymaking as a fluid and rather contingent process, in which three relatively independent streams must converge for an issue to reach the decision agenda. The streams are: the problem stream, the politics stream, and the policy stream. The problem stream concerns how issues are recognized as problems in the first place. This stream is where all the issues, or problems, in society are floating around in a chaotic way, like in a “primeval soup” (Kingdon, 1995), competing for public and policymaker attention. The “primeval soup” is a metaphor used to describe the broad and changing mix of policy issues, and proposals that exist before gaining attention when they enter the formal policy agenda. It is a space where ideas, potential solutions, and perspectives are continually proposed, debated, and reshaped by different actors. Triggering

¹ The section on the theoretical background draws on materials previously developed within the FIERCE project, particularly the D1.1 Report on Detailed Research and Methodological Guidelines for Case Studies and its mapping of actors, debates, and policy outcomes, as well as the D3.1 Methodological Framework and Guidelines for Comparative Analysis.

mechanisms in this process enable issues to attract attention, e.g., indicators, focusing events, and feedback. Indicators can be systematic measures and the quantifiable size of a problem, such as the number of femicides committed in a year, falling birthrates, cases of sexual harassment at work, women's representation in parties or boards, and the like. Some indicators can emerge as the routine output of monitoring by the government, or by targeted NGOs, which bring new indicators to the public attention. Attention can also be drawn on specific issues through focusing events, e.g., crises, or major happenings, such as an exceptional event like the #MeToo mobilizations, or be derived from the feedback provided to already existing policies (DeLeo, Zohlnhöfer & Zahariadis, 2024, p. 16).

According to Kingdon (1984) the policy stream is where different ideas and positions interact and compete with one another and across time. Some ideas are selected for further consideration, while others get discarded. This vetting process occurs through a process known as "softening up", which involves assessing and narrowing the range of policy alternatives within the policy stream. The "policy community" is "a loose connection of civil servants, interest groups, academics, researchers and consultants (the so-called hidden participants), who engage in working out alternatives to the policy problems of a specific policy field" (Herweg, 2016, p. 132; DeLeo, Zohlnhöfer & Zahariadis, 2024, p. 18).

Finally, the politics stream reflects the broader political environment, including shifts in public mood, elections, interest group activity, civil society organizations and social movements' mobilisation and partisan dynamics. In this stream, decisions are taken on whether there is institutional support, or resistance to change. Decisions can vary over time (non-linearity of the process) and be influenced, for instance by the incumbent government's assessment of the electoral popularity/unpopularity of an issue, but also by public opinion/civil society pressure. Compared to more classic process cycle approaches, the politics stream –in combination with the other streams–, helps to shed light on the role played by the multitude and variety of actors within and beyond the institutions, and how these interact, allowing (or not) for an issue to gain traction on the agenda.

The coupling of the three streams' (policy, politics, problem) is not automatic or sequential, but results from the interaction of specific opportunities and the strategic actions of so-called *policy entrepreneurs*. Unlike rational models that treat policies as direct responses to problems, Kingdon's contribution was to emphasize that problems are socially constructed, and policies may exist before problems are even defined (see Hill, Varone & Lotta, forthcoming, 2026). Actors can also purposely seek problems to justify preferred policy solutions. A key innovation of MSF, in contrast to more linear policy process theories, lies in its emphasis on: 1) the conditions that facilitate and allow the coupling of the different streams, that explain why an issue gets onto the policy agenda and certain solutions are preferred, 2) the fundamental work done by so-called policy entrepreneurs, or "individuals who invest considerable time, energy and resources to promote policy change, help facilitate coupling by demonstrating a connection between their preferred solution and a problem circulating the problem stream" (DeLeo, Zohlnhöfer & Zahariadis, 2024, p. 4). These actors are important for two main reasons: 1. they work out policy ideas, present them to other members of the policy community, and seek to get the backing of the policy community; and 2. they help couple the streams, in the sense that they "lie in wait" until the three streams are ready for coupling, at which point they will capitalize on fleeting opportunities. Entrepreneurs can be both government *insiders* (high-ranking bureaucrats, politicians, street-level bureaucrats) as well as government *outsiders* (issue advocates, experts, academics, activists). In fact, they do not need to be individuals, but can also be entire organizations, who work in their pursuit of policy change and strive to couple the three streams in their favour. Entrepreneurs also show some specific traits, such as high social acuity, strong alliance and coalition building skills, good sense on how to frame and define issues (Zahariadis, 2014) and on how to gather and disseminate information. The MSF also

identifies the role of spill-over/path dependency effect, that is, the impact of one policy change on other policies. Yet, although the approach considers the effects of incrementalism, it critically approaches this by considering the dynamic way in which the streams join and policy windows open. The interest in this sense is placed on the way in which key actors/policy entrepreneurs both inside and outside government operate and whose proposals and actions eventually “come together”. Or as Nikolaos Zahariadis argues: “Collective choice is not merely the derivative of individual efforts aggregated in some fashion but rather the combined result of structural forces and cognitive and affective processes that are highly context dependent” (Zahariadis, 2014, p. 26). However, while the MSF helps to focus on how windows of opportunity open and reach the agenda, the theory is less sharp when it comes to addressing the policy implementation process (Sabatier, 2007; Herweg et al., 2015).

Scholarly applications of the MSF also tend to overlook the critical role that *emotions* play in shaping the policy process, including how emotions influence the actions of policy entrepreneurs and policy decision-makers. While the MSF does acknowledge emotions to some extent through the concept of “public mood”, a key factor in the political stream, described as the “prevailing climate of opinion” (Zahariadis, 2015, p. 468), this emotional dimension remains underexplored. Recent literature, however, is increasingly addressing this gap by introducing emotions right into the MSF. Scholars like Maor (2024) emphasize the need to apply an emotional lens to better understand how emotions interact with the policy problem, policy, and politics stream in shaping policy agendas and eventually outcome. Sociologist Arlie Russell Hochschild (2024; 2016) in her recent books explores the role of emotions in politics primarily through her concept of “emotional labour” and her research into the “deep stories” that shape people’s political views and opinions. Her work highlights emotions as central to political behaviour, identity, and decision-making. Emotions play a crucial role in shaping how individuals, for example, connect with political movements, or (“charismatic”) leaders. Politicians often try to evoke emotions like hope, anger, or fear to build support, while steering clear of shame and guilt that could undermine their own position (Widmann, 2021) - although these latter emotions can be used to target opponents. By incorporating emotions into the framework, it becomes possible to develop more nuanced hypotheses about how emotions also inform agenda-setting, influence policy decision-making, and contribute to the creation of “protective” policy outcomes.

Under the MSF theoretical lens, inclusion, or exclusion of gender issues in policymaking depend on how problems, policies, and politics interact under specific conditions. It is noteworthy that only few papers and studies dealing with gender have referred to this theoretical framework, albeit very often the pattern towards policy decision-making regarding gender issues is influenced by both problems, politics and policy conditions. These have been taken into consideration while working thematically and cross-country with the FIERCE data and results derived from earlier WPs. Taken together, MSF allows us to show that whether gender issues reach the political agenda depends not only on facts or needs, but on how problems are framed, who proposes solutions and when, and how the political climate responds.

2.2.2. Framing Theory as Epistemology and Method: Interrogating Strategic Framing in Policy Contexts

Framing theory is a discursive and interpretive approach that enables the in-depth examination of how political and social issues are problematized in texts (Bacchi, 1999), with particular attention to the underlying assumptions, normative logics, and strategic choices embedded in those framings. As both an epistemological orientation and a methodological approach, the notion of framing is rooted in the understanding that language and discourse are not neutral but constitutive – they shape what is seen as problematic, which solutions are proposed, and whose voices are legitimized or excluded in the process.

Drawing on Verloo (2005, p. 20), frames are understood as “organising principles that transform fragmentary or incidental information into a structured and meaningful problem, in which a solution is implicitly or explicitly enclosed”. Frames are thus conceptual lenses that structure meaning and enable actors to make sense of political realities.

In FIERCE, we adopted a shared definition of frame analysis as the study of the discursive construction of norms, beliefs, and perceptions that are embedded in texts (Bacchi, 1999; 2009; Snow & Benford, 1988; Verloo, 2005). A frame is the basic unit of analysis within this approach, representing the cognitive and normative structures through which actors identify problems and propose solutions. In the realm of policy related analysis, framing approaches are relevant in that they build on both social movement theory and critical policy studies to interrogate how policy actors frame particular social issues and how these framings reflect, reinforce, or contest dominant power relations. This approach is especially pertinent to the study of gender equality policies, where meanings of gender and equality are multiple, contested, and often strategically adapted to fit within existing institutional and political constraints.

In social movement studies, framing is seen as a strategic process. Frames are not merely the product of existing grievances; rather, they are produced through intentional efforts to shape political demands, mobilize support and achieve transformation. As Benford and Snow (2000, p. 614) put it, frames are “action-oriented sets of beliefs and meanings” that serve to inspire and legitimate collective action. They argue that framing processes are central to movement building, as they work “to mobilize potential adherents and constituents, to garner bystander support, and to demobilize antagonists” (Snow & Benford, 1988, p. 198). Movements actively construct diagnostic frames, i.e., identifying problems and attributing blame; prognostic frames, proposing solutions and strategies, and motivational frames, encouraging participation and engagement. These elements are foundational to how movements articulate grievances and define themselves in relation to their goals and adversaries.

In FIERCE, we take this framework into the policy realm, where political and institutional actors – government officials, bureaucrats, advocacy groups – also engage in framing practices to shape policy agendas and debates. Strategic framing plays a key role here. As discussed by Verloo (2005) and Pollack and Hafner-Burton (2000), strategic framing refers to the dynamic process by which actors seek to align their own frames with the dominant policy discourse or institutional priorities. For example, framing gender equality as beneficial for economic efficiency or democratic legitimacy serves to embed feminist demands within pre-existing institutional goals, potentially increasing their acceptability and uptake. However, such strategic adaptations can also reduce the transformative potential of feminist interventions, as they risk aligning with logics that reinforce the status quo rather than challenge it.

This strategic use of frames is also emphasized in critical policy analysis, where Bacchi (2005) notes that policy actors deliberately shape problem representations to legitimize certain political outcomes. The power of framing lies in its ability to make visible how these frames are constructed, how they shift across contexts, and how they include or exclude particular interpretations, actors, and interests. In gender equality policymaking, framing has been particularly effective in revealing the multiplicity of meanings attributed to concepts like “equality,” “empowerment,” or “diversity,” and the ways in which some meanings become dominant while others are marginalized (Verloo, 2007).

The framing approach builds on these theoretical insights. It focuses on how problems and solutions are articulated in texts, as well as on the roles and responsibilities attributed to various actors. Framing theory also emphasizes the element of silences, following Bacchi’s (1999) framework, which draws attention to what is left unproblematic or unspoken in the framing. Silences reveal the boundaries of the discourse and point to excluded alternatives or counter-frames that are rendered invisible. Identifying

silences allows researchers to unpack the normative assumptions of dominant frames and to consider what other meanings or perspectives are systematically marginalized.

Importantly for the FIERCE objectives, the framing approach pays attention to the broader political and institutional context in which frames are produced. The context includes political opportunity structures, the institutional frameworks of policymaking, the timing and sequencing of policy debates, and the power dynamics among actors. This contextual focus is relevant for understanding how frames travel across levels (local, national, transnational) and how they are taken up, resisted, or reshaped through political processes. As Ferree (2009, p. 90) argues, framing becomes more dynamic when complemented by analyses of the political processes through which texts are created, interpreted, and mobilized. In this way, it goes beyond textual interpretation to engage with the material and strategic dimensions of policymaking.

Our approach also draws on insights from comparative studies of frame variation and alignment. Snow, Vliegenthart and Corrigan-Brown (2007) show that frame variation across countries is influenced by contextual factors, which shape how problems are contextually defined, and solutions are envisioned. We extend this line of inquiry to policy analysis by examining how frames vary across institutional settings and national contexts, and how frame alignment processes are deployed to create discursive bridges between policy actors and their audiences. This is particularly relevant for cross-national studies of gender equality policies, where notions of equality are embedded in diverse cultural and political traditions, and where institutional constraints shape the strategic choices available to actors.

Framing has thus proven to be an effective epistemological and analytical lens for identifying both the discursive constructions and the strategic calculations involved in policy framing. By paying close attention to how gender issues are framed – what is said, what is left out, who speaks, and in which context – framing enables a more nuanced understanding of how gender equality is negotiated within policy processes. It illuminates how competing frames coexist, how dominant frames marginalize alternatives, and how strategic framing can simultaneously advance and constrain feminist goals.

The rationale for combining the MSF with framing theory lies in their complementary analytical strengths rather than in any competition between them. MSF offers a dynamic model for understanding when and under what conditions actors succeed in coupling problems, policies, and politics, thereby advancing issues onto the policy agenda and into decision-making processes. Framing theory, in turn, sheds light on how these actors strategically construct and communicate problems and solutions to align with prevailing institutional logics, mobilize allies, and neutralize opponents. Importantly, framing theory also engages directly with structural power relations by examining how dominant discourses shape what is seen as a problem, what solutions are considered legitimate, and whose voices are included or excluded – dimensions that enrich and extend the structural insights of the streams approach. By integrating MSF's focus on the timing and structural conditions of agenda-setting with framing theory's attention to the discursive, strategic, and power-laden dimensions of actor intervention, we gain a more comprehensive understanding of how gender-related issues enter, move through, or fail to reach the political agenda. This combined lens captures both the structural constraints and the meaning-making processes, revealing how social actors navigate political conditions and deploy rhetorical, symbolic, and affective resources in pursuit of policy change.

2.3. Methodological Approach

2.3.1. Methods²

This comparative report draws on extensive qualitative and quantitative research carried out within the frameworks of WP1 and WP2. The project explored anti-gender and anti-feminist movements (WP1) and feminist movements (WP2) through three distinct research streams, based on different methods adopted in data collection: interviews, CFA, and DNA. Together, these methods aimed to capture the articulation of discursive and strategic repertoires of anti-gender and feminist actors, as well as key factors underlying policy processes, in the countries covered by the FIERCE project, between 2010 and 2023.

The following sections briefly outline these three research streams, describing the methods, samples, and analytical approaches applied to the empirical material. More detailed methodological information is available in the WP1 (D1.2) and WP2 (D2.2) fieldwork reports, which are publicly accessible on the project's website.

Interviews

In WP1, we aimed to examine the strategies, discourses, and organizational dynamics of anti-gender and anti-feminist actors across eight countries. Semi-structured interviews were conducted to gather insights into respondents' views on gender equality, reproductive rights, LGBTIQ+ issues, and educational policies. The interviews explored core advocacy topics, perceived societal threats, strategic repertoires, organizational models, policy impact, institutional engagement, and national and transnational alliances.

Securing interviews with anti-gender and anti-feminist actors proved challenging due to ideological opposition, concerns about the project's feminist framing, and political sensitivities. Of the 164 individuals contacted, only 25% agreed to participate, resulting in a total of 41 interviews, each lasting between one and two hours. Interviews were conducted either in person or online, depending on logistical circumstances and participants' preferences.

To mitigate limited direct access, the research adopted supplementary strategies. Interviews were sought with individuals sympathetic to certain anti-gender positions, including trans-exclusionary gender-critical feminists and right-wing or conservative political actors. Additionally, in contexts where interviews were unattainable, even after several attempts and perseverance, publicly available materials, such as interviews, speeches, podcasts, and videos from media outlets that featured anti-gender and anti-feminist actors, were systematically collected and analysed. Altogether, 70 alternative sources were incorporated to address the thematic areas outlined in the interview protocol, enabling a broader comparative analysis across national contexts.

In WP2, we collected and analysed interviews with feminist activists and pro-feminist politicians, who provided valuable insights into the strategies, discourses, and organizational models that define contemporary feminist movements. The interviews examined central topics such as gender-based violence, reproductive rights, LGBTIQ+ rights, labour struggles, and feminist critiques of patriarchy and neoliberalism. Participants also discussed organizational histories, ideological underpinnings, challenges posed by anti-gender movements, strategies for activism, coalition building, and policy impact and institutional engagement.

² The section on methods draws on materials previously developed within the FIERCE project, particularly the D1.2 and D2.2 fieldwork reports.

A total of 240 semi-structured interviews were conducted, including 163 with feminist activists and 69 with political representatives or policymakers supportive of feminist initiatives, averaging approximately 20 and 10 interviews per country, respectively. The purposive sampling strategy ensured diversity, capturing insights from individuals active in grassroots collectives, formal NGOs, informal networks, and institutional settings. Interviews ranged from one to two hours and were conducted either in person or online.

Across both work packages, interviews were recorded and transcribed with informed consent, ensuring compliance with ethical standards of confidentiality and privacy. Thematic analysis was conducted using MAXQDA, a software employed to systematically identify patterns and insights within the interview transcripts and supplementary materials. To ensure confidentiality, interview quotes are attributed using the following format: country, type of actor (feminist activist – FA, feminist political stakeholder – FPS or anti-gender actor – AG), and interview number (e.g., Spain, interview with feminist activist, FA12).

Critical Frame Analysis (CFA)

CFA was applied to political and social movement documents produced by anti-gender and anti-feminist actors (WP1) as well as feminist actors (WP2). Our analysis aimed to identify how gender categories are framed, used, and communicated. The core analytical dimensions include diagnosis (how the problem is defined), prognosis (which solutions are proposed), and voice (who is positioned to speak, or act). This included examining major and minor frames within the project's five key thematic areas as well as intersectional patterns, silences, and the role of emotions. Particular attention was paid to potential policy influence or impact, as reflected in the analysed documents. In our research, we build on the foundational elements of CFA – diagnosis, prognosis, and voice – and expand the framework by adding two further dimensions: context and silences. These additions enable us to analyse how frames operate not just within texts, but within political fields marked by contestation, negotiation, and exclusion. Silences help us detect which dimensions of a problem are ignored, while contextual analysis sheds light on how political actors seize or miss opportunities to influence the agenda.

The primary unit of analysis was a campaign, conceptualized as a sustained political process encompassing both a policy dimension (e.g., legislative proposals) and an activist dimension (e.g., mobilization for or against policy change). CFA was used to analyse documents emerging in the context of these campaigns. Each partner proposed the most salient campaigns for each work package, covering national contexts between 2010 and 2023. Based on an overview of these proposals, one anti-gender campaign (WP1) focusing on LGBTIQ+ rights and one feminist campaign (WP2) on gender-based violence were selected from each country, as these topics were prominent across all cases. The selection of the second campaign in each WP was determined individually by partners. For WP1, the second anti-gender campaigns often focused on education or reproductive rights, while WP2 campaigns were more diverse, covering issues such as LGBTIQ+ rights, labour market, reproductive rights, and education.

In total, each country analysed four campaigns: two anti-gender campaigns within WP1 and two feminist campaigns within WP2. For each campaign, a minimum of five parliamentary debate interventions (political texts) and ten documents from social movement actors (activist texts) were coded per country.

The analysis was conducted using MAXQDA software. Coding integrated both predefined (closed) and emergent (open) codes. Closed codes were based on predefined frames identified through the FIERCE literature reviews. Open codes captured additional frames emerging from the empirical material. Frames and problem statements were classified as major, minor, or marginal, and code sets were established in the software to link different code elements that compose frames (code marker combinations, e.g., problem statement-active actor-passive actor-underlying norm). Quotes from the analysed

documents are attributed using the following format: country, type of actor (feminist – FEM or anti-gender – AG), type of document (social movement document – SOCMOV or parliamentary debate – PD), and document number (e.g., SLOVENIA_AG_PD_07).

Discourse Network Analysis (DNA)

We applied Discourse Network Analysis (DNA) to identify how policy debates unfold in the public arena, focusing on national newspaper coverage in which a variety of actors made known their positions on a variety of gender-related policy issues. DNA is a specific type of social network analysis (SNA) that identifies advocacy coalitions based on actors' policy preferences, transforming text data, such as newspaper articles, into structured statements capturing who speaks about which policy issues and the stance they take.

Data collection for DNA began with a predefined list of keywords reflecting specific events, campaigns, and debates. These keywords were used to retrieve articles, news items, and reports from a comparable selection of newspapers in each country, covering a continuum of five years within the period from 2015 to 2023, chosen with respect to contextually specific events and timing of debates. At least two prominent newspapers were selected per country; one moderate-left and one moderate-right; to ensure balanced political perspectives. In countries with more fragmented political landscapes, additional newspapers were included to capture diverse voices, with practical considerations such as database availability also influencing selection.

Searches employed the keywords: *gender*, *LGBTIQ+*, and *feminist*, with adjustments for linguistic and contextual relevance for each country case. Where necessary, terms like *gender equality*, *same-sex marriage*, *mandatory shared custody*, or *Istanbul Convention* were added to capture country-specific debates.

In total, 56,840 articles were sampled, resulting in 23,737 coded statements. The scale and intensity of political debates varied significantly across countries. Turkey stood out due to its large population, intense discussions on gender-based violence and the Istanbul Convention, and a complex media landscape that required broader newspaper sampling. Conversely, Italy, Poland, and Slovenia yielded fewer coded statements, despite high numbers of collected articles, often because relevant debates fell outside the coding framework, appeared in excluded opinion pieces, or involved limited engagement from anti-gender or feminist actors.

The coding process involved identifying policy statements in the newspaper articles and recording details such as the date, the actor or organization speaking, the policy issue addressed, and the actor's stance on the issue (positive or negative), using the Discourse Network Analyzer software. This work was guided by a shared codebook containing 83 concepts across key thematic areas, including marriage, education, health and reproductive rights, labour market, gender-based violence, and LGBTIQ+ rights. The codebook was initially developed before the coding began. It was then refined and expanded inductively during the preliminary stages of coding to include new codes that the data revealed. The national coding teams met bi-weekly to discuss the news items on which they were not clear and to retain consistency in the application of the codes across the teams.

Subsequently, the coded data was then analysed using the statistical R software to generate visual outputs such as charts of the most active actors and debated topics, time-series graphs indicating peaks in discourse, and network maps illustrating connections among actors and concepts. Two-mode networks displayed links between organizations and specific policy issues, while one-mode networks revealed

how actors clustered based on shared positions. Measures like degree and betweenness centrality identified the most connected and influential actors, while community detection techniques highlighted cohesive subgroups within the networks.

Overall, the use of DNA enabled a bird's eye view of the policy fields in each of the national contexts, providing the research with clear quantitative representation of the degree of intensity of debates, which debates preoccupied the national scene more and which actors were likely to get their voices nationally heard. Looking at the rankings produced in this manner, we were able to also delineate comparatively the relative significance of each policy issue area which this research focused on. We were able to identify the kinds of discourse coalitions that emerged in different contexts. While in most cases, this data corroborated the findings emerging from other data streams, occasionally it also revealed that some issues that mattered more to activists from both camps did not always play out as intensely at the national media scene as expected based on qualitative data.

2.3.2. Comparative Approach

This report adopts a comparative analytical approach to examine how anti-gender and feminist actors engage across five key thematic policy areas in eight national contexts. It builds upon collaborative work conducted in cross-country thematic working groups. The formation of these groups was informed by key insights from WP1 and WP2. The five selected thematic areas were intentionally chosen to facilitate cross-country comparison, reflect intersectional dynamics, and align the analysis with real-world policy challenges. In total, six thematic groups were established, each focusing on a distinct gender-relevant and policy-oriented area: (1) LGBTIQ+ rights; (2) gender-based violence; (3) health and reproductive rights; (4) labour market, migration, and care; and (5) intersectionality; and (6) democratic innovations (purposely introduced in view of D3.3, findings from this group are therefore not included in the present report). The groups were initially formed based on the teams' expressed interests, expertise in their respective country cases, and insights gained during empirical data collection and preliminary analysis at the national level.

Each thematic group held at least one meeting prior to every monthly plenary session of the FIERCE consortium, from December 2024 to June 2025. Group leaders were responsible for organizing these meetings, where findings and ongoing dilemmas were discussed. Updates and key results from the thematic groups were regularly shared and discussed during the FIERCE plenary meetings. The primary task of the thematic groups was to identify the most relevant analytical questions within their thematic areas, drawing on data collected in WP1 and WP2 (interviews, CFA, and DNA). Each group was responsible for producing one or more draft papers using dimensions from the theoretical framework set out in the project's methodological manual for WP3 to develop a comparative, multidimensional analysis. The groups determined which theoretical dimensions and empirical cases to include as well as actors (anti-gender/anti-feminist or feminist), prioritizing relevance and saliency. Importantly, the groups were not obliged to address all theoretical dimensions or compare all country cases within each theme, allowing flexibility to reflect the specificities and relevance of the data and context.

This report builds on the draft papers prepared by thematic groups, as well as on the data and analysis presented in the WP1 and WP2 fieldwork reports. Initially, we extracted empirical material from each paper focusing on the continuum of policymaking – from direct policy outcomes to more indirect influences exerted through agenda-setting and strategic framing, through which actors deliberately shape problem representations to legitimize specific political outcomes. Where necessary, we complemented this material with data from the WP1 and WP2 fieldwork reports. For each thematic area, empirical material was reorganized and analysed with an exclusive focus on policy processes and

outcomes, intentionally detaching it from broader conceptual debates to foreground the policy dimension.

To do so, our comparative framework integrated both epistemological and methodological dimensions, drawing specifically on MSF and framing theory. MSF facilitates the examination of how policy windows emerge, highlighting the conditions and actors that influence agenda-setting and policy output. Framing theory, meanwhile, enables a deeper interrogation of how issues are problematized, how solutions are articulated, and the underlying normative logics and strategic framings involved. Together, these approaches provide insight into how discourses and strategic repertoires are deployed to navigate institutional structures and political opportunity contexts.

We employed a mixed-methods strategy that triangulates data from interviews, CFA conducted on policy and activist documents, and DNA conducted on newspaper data. Although the project aimed to apply a unified methodological framework across all three research streams, country-specific contexts, data collection challenges, and the characteristics of national samples necessitated methodological adaptations for this comparative report. Rather than enforcing rigid comparative metrics, our analysis seeks to trace trends, dynamics, and key distinctions across countries and thematic areas. Our goal is not to produce direct one-to-one comparisons but to highlight emerging patterns, similarities, and differences within individual thematic areas. This approach enables us to identify shared challenges, context-specific nuances, and cross-national dynamics in gender-related policymaking.

2.4. Thematic Areas

In the following sections, we present the main part of our multidimensional cross-country comparative analysis, organized around five key thematic areas: (1) LGBTIQ+ rights; (2) gender-based violence; (3) health and reproductive rights; (4) labour market, migration, and care; and (5) intersectionality. As previously noted, the selection of country cases and actors for each thematic area was guided by thematic relevance, the availability of empirical data, and the diversity of political and institutional contexts. Accordingly, each thematic section begins with a contextual background and a brief rationale for the selection of specific country cases and actors. Next, we highlight key findings from the DNA, which provides an overview of the publicly debated topics within each thematic area, as well as the saliency of these themes across country cases. The subsequent analysis in each section examines findings related to policymaking processes across the relevant country contexts. The analysis is structured around the three streams of the MSF, which serve as the main analytical categories for interpreting empirical material derived from interviews and CFA.

In the *problem stream*, we explore how certain issues come to be recognized as public problems. This process is often triggered by indicators (e.g., statistical measures), focusing events (e.g., crises or mobilizations), or feedback from existing policies that highlight ongoing challenges or failures. In the *policy stream*, we analyse various policy ideas and solutions that are proposed, debated, and refined. Finally, in the *politics stream*, we reflect the broader political climate, including electoral dynamics, public opinion, and institutional support or resistance, all of which influence the timing and feasibility of policy adoption.

While politics stream inevitably involves actors situated within each specific field, before turning to the thematic analyses that follow, we want to contextualize this with an explanation of the broader network of actors as revealed through DNA. Our DNA analysis is unique in this regard by providing also a quantitative approach to comparing gender-related policy issues and the actors involved. Providing a cross-cutting overview relevant to all the thematic areas explored in the following chapters, DNA has enabled us to explore across country cases which types of actors are more likely to enter policy debates and who

occupies more voice in the political field in connection to their weight in policy positions. For a perspective that moves beyond each country case, we can take into account the top-twenty rankings for political actors in each of the country cases. When these rankings are combined and the actors that make it to the top of the lists are coded in terms of their organizational characteristics, we can clearly see that the two major actors in the policy debates on gender equality are occupied by political parties and a variety of NGOs, followed by professional associations, business associations and labour unions. This data speaks to the whole terrain, encompassing all policy issue areas making up the focus of this research.

The rise to the top of political parties as the actors who speak most on multiple gender-related issues is unsurprising given the broad-based nature of political parties. Of the 47 political parties that found a place in the top-twenty charts, we identified 23 of them as left-wing or centre-left wing parties, 18 of them as right-wing or centre-right wing parties, and the rest as centrist. While these categorizations are not necessarily fixed, the distribution nevertheless reflects the ways in which gender policies preoccupy all ideological positions.

In terms of the composition of NGOs, feminist, and LGBTIQ+ NGOs outweigh anti-feminist and anti-gender NGOs in almost all cases, suggesting the capacity of these actors despite changing political circumstances. We can see a total of 35 feminist and pro-LGBTIQ NGOs and advocacy groups combined, and four anti-gender NGOs, excluding denominational institutions which appear to ally with anti-gender positions. While in most countries it is predominantly right-wing political parties that advocate regressing gender equality, in Poland and Slovenia such positions are also strongly advanced by actors outside the political spectrum. The prominence of pro-gender equality NGOs and advocacy groups is striking when contrasted with a general right-wing turn almost everywhere. Multiple interpretations are possible, requiring a combined reading with qualitative findings of this research as well as new research questions focusing on which mechanisms facilitate which voices to translate into concrete proposals in either direction.

The participation in policy debates also includes a variety of other actors whose core focus is not gender, such as professional associations, business associations, labour unions, and religious leaderships. High in the rankings, we find business associations in Denmark; professional associations in Spain and Turkey; labour unions in Denmark, Turkey and Italy; universities in Slovenia; organizations with a rights-based focus in Greece; and religious institutions in Italy, Greece and Slovenia. These findings give us a glimpse of the cross-cutting nature of gender-related policymaking as well as the significant space gender occupies in the general political field. The distribution also gives us an indication of which gender-related policy fields are more predominant in the specific country cases.

Finally, in addition to the three MSF streams, our analysis also incorporates framing theory as a cross-cutting dynamic embedded within all three streams, shaping how problems are defined, how solutions are articulated, how political feasibility is assessed, and how frames align with contextual factors across national cases. Each thematic section concludes by summarizing key insights and their implications for policymaking.

2.4.1. LGBTIQ+ Rights³

³ This section is based on the work conducted within the thematic group LGBTIQ+ rights, drawing in particular on material from the draft paper *Framing Protection, Mobilizing Fear: The "Best Interest of the Child" in Anti-Gender Mobilizations* by Roman Kuhar, Andreas Beyer Gregersen, Anna Lavizzari, Ayşe Alnıaçık, Guillermo Fernandez Vazquez, Magdalena Muszel, Özlem Altan and Rok Smrdelj. It also incorporates material from the WP1 and WP2 fieldwork reports, particularly the DNA data prepared by Özlem Altan Olcay.

LGBTIQ+ rights is the policy area in which the most significant and transformative changes have occurred in recent decades. Across Europe and much of the world, there have been notable shifts in public attitudes toward LGBTIQ+ individuals and substantial policy advances since the mid-20th century, including the decriminalization of homosexuality and the recognition of same-sex unions or, in some countries, same-sex marriage (Ayoub & Stoeckl, 2024). In all studied country cases, LGBTIQ+ rights are also in focus for not only LGBTIQ+ organisations, but also the feminist movements. This reflects that gender and sexuality issues have become increasingly intertwined, reflecting historical collaborations and growing intersectional solidarity between feminist and LGBTIQ+ movements (della Porta & Bonu Rosenkranz, 2025), particularly evident in countries like Denmark, Slovenia, Turkey, Poland, Italy, France.

Despite advances, LGBTIQ+ rights have also been facing several waves of coordinated resistance, often led by religious and conservative actors. As Kuhar and Paternotte (2017) note, LGBTIQ+ issues have provoked the largest mobilizations within anti-gender movements and there appears to be an ongoing backlash, across the world. Civil partnership laws and same-sex marriage have frequently triggered such campaigns, as seen in Spain, Italy, France, Greece, and Slovenia. In some contexts, including Slovenia, anti-gender movements have successfully blocked marriage equality for several years. However, the scope of opposition extends beyond marriage to encompass broader concerns about family and kinship structures, including debates over same-sex adoption, surrogacy, and reproductive technologies (Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017), as well as opposition to sexual education and public visibility through pride events and trans rights advocacy. As a result, LGBTIQ+ rights remain an extremely polarized field with most often clear demarcating lines between “us” and “them”.

Although feminist and LGBTIQ+ movements in Europe have increasingly begun to collaborate on promoting LGBTIQ+ rights, exemplified by the development of transfeminist stances in particularly Southern Europe, this engagement faces massive resistance from anti-gender movements that have turned LGBTIQ+ issues into central symbols of perceived societal decline and disorder. LGBTIQ+ rights are posited at the heart of the ideological construct of “gender ideology”, often portrayed by opponents as a shared agenda among activists, public officials, and left-wing politicians. Given the persistent and influential negative focus on LGBTIQ+ rights by anti-gender actors, this thematic section specifically examines anti-gender campaigns.

The relevance of this thematic area within gender equality debates was highlighted in our DNA analysis, which revealed a striking finding: LGBTIQ+ rights is the concept on which the greatest number of statements were made in the aggregate data from all the countries. Similarly, several other concepts that are part of this thematic area also drew remarkable attention. In DNA coding, we utilized broad concepts such as LGBTIQ+ rights in the labour market, LGBTIQ+ rights abroad and gender ideology to capture broad debates in this policy area. We also included the following concepts to capture debates on more specific areas: hate crime legislation; conversion therapy; gender recognition legislation; gender transitioning; bathroom access; access to affordable and non-discriminatory sexual and reproductive health care services; adoption rights; rights of children of same-sex couple. As per usual, country specific codes were added where necessary.

While other concepts in other thematic areas were also subject to some disagreement, the concepts related to LGBTIQ+ rights stand out as the concepts drawing the highest degrees of disagreement. The chart below, aggregating the data across cases, reveals this finding (Figure 1). This, we propose, reflects

the growth in the transnational anti-gender backlash and can be considered a warning signal for the possible vulnerabilities in policy achievements toward LGBTIQ+ rights.

Figure 1. Most controversial debates (aggregate figures adjusted for country sizes)

In addition to this observation at the aggregate level, we can say that concepts relating to LGBTIQ+ rights were especially pronounced in Italy and Poland. In Italy, the list of top 20 debates included 10 concepts related to LGBTIQ+ rights, while in Poland this figure was 8. Slovenia was a close runner up with 7 of the top 20 debates on LGBTIQ+ rights.

In the Italian case, we observe that while LGBTIQ+ issues are a strong component of cultural production and the public conversation in the country, policy advances on the same issues are slow and scarce. And yet the discrepancy between the two realms can also be an opportunity for policy work in the coming decades.

Figure 2. Top 20 debated concepts, Italian case

In the Slovenian case (as also present to a certain degree in the Italian case), there is a discrepancy between a large degree of agreement on LGBTIQ+ rights and the vociferous opposition to specific policies that will make these rights possible. This indicates the strategy of anti-gender and neoconservative actors to not openly voice discriminatory stances toward LGBTIQ+ issues but continue to oppose a variety of demands with other rationales and strategies. This is both a constraint and opportunity, requiring

active work to promote public awareness on this discrepancy and to achieve broader public consensus on policy tools that will introduce and protect LGBTIQ+ rights more fully.

Figure 3. Top 20 debated concepts, Slovenian case

The Polish case reveals a more visible opposition to LGBTIQ+ rights in general, requiring different strategies to look into the contours of this opposition, the actors involved in the coalitions, which the DNA data also does: in the data on the most vocal actors whose opinions are captured in newspaper articles, we see the significant position of the Catholic Church as well as well-resourced right-wing think tanks, suggesting the role played by key actors with sizeable resources and influence in generating the oppositional stance.

Figure 4. Top 20 debated concepts, Polish case

Given the salience of debates on LGBTIQ+ issues across all country contexts, the following qualitative analysis takes up six country cases together (Denmark, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, Italy, and Turkey), with an eye to the ways in which anti-gender activists position their anti-LGBTIQ+ positions in a number of different policy areas, always with the argument of protecting children and families.

Through this comparative perspective on anti-gender mobilizations in six country cases, the analysis builds on the empirical material from CFA of anti-gender activist documents and parliamentary debates across the six country cases, to explore the strategic deployment of the “best interest of the child” frame. This framing, one of the most prominent in recent anti-gender campaigns, is deployed to oppose

a wide array of issues; from marriage equality and same-sex parenting to abortion, education, and transgender rights. More specifically, the analysis shows that there is both malleability and inconsistency in how this frame is applied across national contexts. This is reflected in different iterations of the “best interest of the child” that are uncovered through the analysis; iterations that present the image of the child in quite different ways.

In these six country cases, we have studied a diverse set of campaigns, ranging right from mobilizations in Denmark against legal gender change for minors to anti-abortion protests in Poland and a prolonged campaign against marriage equality in Slovenia. In Denmark, the analysed campaign consisted of a series of mobilizations against a 2020 law proposal to remove the age limit on legal gender change for minors. In Italy, the campaigns in question have been against a proposed law on homotransphobia as well as the alias career policy, which allows trans persons to continue using preferred personal names in the education system. In Poland, the analysis has focused on both anti-abortion mobilizations as well as resistance to gender equality policies and LGBTIQ+ rights. In Slovenia, a prolonged campaign against marriage equality and adoption rights for same-sex couples was chosen for analysis. In Spain, two major campaigns have been analysed concerning resistance to abortion legislation and other sexual and reproductive rights as well as opposition to the 2023 “trans law”. Finally, the anti-gender campaign in Turkey from 2019 and forward against gender equality policies in the national education system, framed as “harmful Western” impositions, has also been analysed and compared with the five other cases.

The six country cases have been chosen because they cover a wide range of different anti-gender mobilizations that employ the “best interest of the child” frame, right from marriage equality and same-sex parenting to abortion, education, and transgender rights. Thus, this allows for a robust comparative analysis of how specifically child well-being narratives are constituted and instrumentalized across diverse national contexts.

Given the focus on strategic framing in this comparative analysis, this section primarily elucidates the problem stream regarding anti-feminist and anti-gender resistance to LGBTIQ+ rights across Europe.

Problem stream

In all the six country cases, child well-being narratives function as a form of strategic framing to block or roll back policies, while seeking to effectuate agenda denial on the efforts to promote LGBTIQ+ persons’ interests and rights. Furthermore, we have uncovered through the comparative analysis five iterations of the “best interest of the child” frame, which highlights its strategic adaptability:

- 1) Children as individuals having certain rights
- 2) Children as lacking agency and in need of external protection
- 3) Children as either biologically determined or culturally influenced
- 4) Children as being at risk of inappropriate sexual exposure
- 5) Children as being easily manipulated and indoctrinated

Some of these iterations have already been studied in previous literature. For instance, Brock and Askanus (2023) argue that the ideas of children being violated and manipulated stem from a cultural sacralization of childhood emerging prominently throughout the twentieth century, in which children are thought to embody a “pure state of innocence” that must be shielded as much as possible from the rest of society. This also helps to explain the frequent emergence of moral panics around children, where excessive alarm and fear suddenly spread throughout society because of a perceived danger to

children. What our analysis uniquely reveals is the remarkable malleability of the “best interest of the child” frame, which can assume nearly contradictory forms in the various contexts where it is deployed.

This is particularly noticeable in the analysis of the third iteration (Children as either biologically determined or culturally influenced), which depicts children as either having an essential biological sex or as being vulnerable to cultural influences that can somehow disrupt the functioning of one’s biological sex. In this manner, moral panic about child well-being can be promoted by anti-gender actors in two seemingly contradictory ways, referring to both essentialist ideas about biological sex and cultural influences that disrupt biology. For instance, Turkish anti-gender actors have expressed alarm and sought to spread moral panic about a Ministry of Education campaign slogan – “Are you ready to rewrite?” – based on the argument that this encourages a suppression of “natural” gender roles. In this sense, such gender roles are thought of as being exactly possible to “rewrite” through culture, even though they are at the same time grounded in natural differences.

Similarly, in the campaign against legal gender change for minors in Denmark, anti-gender actors argue that children’s gender identities develop over time, and that children are allowed to experiment with gender roles, but that they should not confuse this with any change to their biological sex that remains immutable. In such iterations of the “best interest of the child” frame, anti-gender actors seem to recognize, to some extent, a dynamic relation between culture and biology, gender and sex, but they strategically frame this recognition within an alarmist rhetoric of culture distorting what is “natural”.

Another example of this malleability in child well-being narratives is that children can be presented both as rights-bearing individuals, who are treated in this respect the same as adults, and as not yet fully formed beings who lack agency and cannot determine what is in their own interests. The claim that children have certain rights are often coupled by anti-gender actors to the promotion of heterosexual parenting and the core family. For instance, in the Slovenian campaign against introducing same-sex marriage, it is proclaimed as evident that the absence of a father or a mother in children’s lives is traumatic and violates their rights. In contrast, the nuclear family is presented as the natural model and most suitable for any child’s development, which cannot be realized properly in other family forms, designated as so-called “disorganized” families.

At the same time, children can also be framed as both cognitively and emotionally immature, entailing that they cannot have any right to self-determination compared to adults but must be protected from external influence. In most of the country cases, it is the parents that are thought to have the right to educate their own children and take decisions on their behalf, even though there are some exceptions to this where parents can also be suspected by anti-gender actors of corrupting their own children. Notably, in the Danish campaign against legal gender change for minors, parents of trans children are often put in suspicion for contributing to, or even manipulatively pushing, the “falsehood” that their own children are transgender.

This coupling of the “best interest of the child” frame with family discourses can also be adapted to ultraconservative ideology of the core family as the only “proper” family and the foundation for a well-functioning society. This is, for instance, the case in Italy where both right-wing politicians and anti-gender activists repeatedly claim that children need to grow up in a core family. Similarly, the core family is conceived as the only real family in the Slovenian campaign against same-sex marriage, implying that if this family form is threatened the whole society and the continuation of the nation are under attack:

“We demand and expect the state to protect the family, which is the only one that ensures the survival of the nation. We reject the devaluation of the family of father, mother and children at the

expense of gender theory and an extremely distorted understanding of equality.”
(SLOVENIA_AG_SOCMOV_03)

In this view, children’s well-being in core families is conceived as essential for a well-functioning society, making it also important to safeguard that children grow up to become heterosexual adults that are themselves ready to form new core families. In this context, it can be argued that in these campaigns children are symbolic figures of both the present and the future; a living potential onto which activists project both their ideals and hopes as well as their anxieties and indignations (Gilliam & Gulløv, 2023).

Policy stream

Even though the implications of this type of strategic framing for contributing to the creation of windows of opportunity for policy change or agenda denial as to the promotion of LGBTIQ+ rights have not been studied in-depth within this comparative analysis, it stands clear that “the best interest of the children” frame has a significant political impact across Europe. In other words, when the politics stream and the policy stream align together with these child well-being narratives, there is an opportunity for anti-gender actors to realize their agendas on a policy level, which in several of the country cases has led to either the rolling back of existing policies or the introduction of new ones in recent years. For instance, in Italy, the so-called Zan Bill on combating homotransphobia was defeated in the Senate in 2021 with reference to its proclaimed impact on children and young people, while anti-abortion mobilizations referring to the rights of unborn children in Poland have contributed to the Constitutional Tribunal’s ruling, also in 2020, which restricted the right to abortion even further than before in the country.

Across the six country cases, there are particularly four key policy areas where the “best interest of children” frame has been effectively deployed by anti-gender actors: marriage equality and same-sex parenting, abortion, education, and transgender rights. In Slovenia, the frame has been applied as a justification for legal rejection of same-sex marriage with the claim that the well-being of children is best protected in a core family model with both a mother and a father. As already mentioned, child well-being in the form of unborn children’s rights have particularly been prominent in Poland where it is discursively connected to nationalist narratives about abortion, related to demographic decline. Education is also a key policy area in many countries ranging from Poland and Slovenia to Italy and Turkey, with the anti-gender movement in Turkey having obstructed several gender equality reforms on education in recent years. In this context, anti-gender actors mainly present children as passive and vulnerable beings in need of protection from the pervasive influence of “gender ideology”.

Finally, child well-being narratives are also continuously applied in the resistance to transgender rights and particularly gender-affirmative treatment for minors in countries such as Denmark and Italy. In Denmark, this has effectively led to agenda denial in the Danish Parliament regarding a policy proposal on introducing legal gender recognition for minors, which was already proposed in 2019 by the Social Democratic government. However, even though “the best interest of children” remains a powerful frame, it is not always successful and can be counteracted by feminist and LGBTIQ+ movements advancing their own claims about what is best for children, e.g. in the case of gender-affirmative treatment for minors. Thus, the policy stream is in this context closely connected to the politics stream.

Politics stream

It is hardly surprising that the concrete deployment of the “best interest of the child” frame to specific issues is closely connected to the politics stream in the sense that a certain iteration and application of this frame can be highly successful in one political context, while being almost entirely dismissed or ignored in another. For instance, the specific iteration of this frame in terms of unborn children having certain rights analysed in Poland does not resonate in a country such as Denmark where the abortion

limit was raised from 12 to 18 weeks in 2025. As another case in point, the framing of children being harmed by growing up in LGBTIQ+ families does not resonate as much in a country such as Spain, where the right for same-sex couples to adopt children was already introduced in 2005, as in Slovenia where this sort of iteration has played a decisive role in several major campaigns against same-sex marriage. However, that “the best interest of the child” frame is still being continuously applied and adapted to such different political cultures across Europe testifies to its remarkable malleability and strength.

The effectiveness of the “best interest of child” frame also depends on the hegemonic and alternative discourses unfolding in temporally specific political moments, and the general discourse on children in a certain period and political context, which is testified by the fact that previous moral panics on children took place in distinct waves of mobilization and public attention. For instance, during the 1950s in the US, male homosexuals were targeted as “sexual psychopaths” abusing children, while the so-called Satanic panic in North America with unsubstantiated stories of child abuse in Satanic rituals mainly evolved through the 1980s (Marwick et al., 2024). In the case of contemporary anti-gender movements, what proves most effective is when a negative spiral evolves with both increasing hysteria about “children in danger” in present-day society due to numerous threats and increasing attacks against LGBTIQ+ persons. Notably, this has in recent years also resulted in the “anti-gay” legislation introduced under the pretext of shielding children from cultural and ideological danger in countries such as Russia, Hungary, and Bulgaria (Takács, Fobear & Schmitsek, 2022). As mentioned previously, discourses on endangered children connect in the contemporary period with other discourses such as the promotion of the core family model and rhetoric about “gender ideology”. These mutually reinforce each other and potentially shape broader public discourse. However, this also points to a potential for feminist and LGBTIQ+ movements to strike back: if child well-being can be discursively reframed and associated with the advancement of both women’s and LGBTIQ+ persons’ rights, this can be used as a lever to resist and combat anti-gender movements across Europe.

Main Takeaways

These results establish that the “best interest of the child” frame is an extraordinarily flexible tool for advancing anti-gender agendas and influence the political system through a rhetoric that seems neutral in the sense that everyone can agree to the basic statement that children are in special need of protection. In this regard, anti-gender actors construct diagnostic frames that recast policies such as same-sex marriage, gender recognition, or inclusive sexual education as threats to children’s safety and well-being. The framing strategically leverages widely accepted normative beliefs about childhood as a protected sphere, establishing the discourse with strong emotional resonance and moral urgency.

Through this framing process, anti-gender actors also position themselves as policy entrepreneurs, presenting themselves as defenders of children’s welfare. This ostensibly neutral stance helps obscure their underlying ideological objectives and lends legitimacy to their claims. By casting themselves as guardians of universal values rather than as ideologically driven actors, they seek to broaden their appeal beyond conservative circles and exert influence within mainstream political debates.

The analysis further reveals significant malleability and inconsistency in how this frame is applied across different national contexts, reflecting processes of frame alignment. Anti-gender actors adapt their discourse to align with prevailing policy narratives, cultural norms, and public sentiments in each country, thereby increasing the likelihood of policy uptake, or, conversely, policy obstruction. The “best interest of the child” frame’s adaptability illustrates how anti-gender actors navigate diverse institutional environments and political opportunity structures, showing how frames can travel across borders and yet remain strategically tailored to local contexts.

Finally, the deployment of child-wellbeing narratives functions as a depoliticization strategy. By framing their opposition as merely “common sense” protection of children, anti-gender actors obscure their ideological motives and seek to present themselves as neutral, moderate voices. In this connection, the imagery of the child at risk is also heavily emotionally invested through the associations of innocence and vulnerability requiring both protection and care.

2.4.2. Gender-Based Violence⁴

Over the past decades, gender-based violence (GBV) has emerged as a significant political issue, largely due to sustained feminist mobilizations (Krizsán & Roggeband, 2018b). Since the mid-2010s, Europe has witnessed a renewed surge of feminist activism around GBV, exemplified by the #MeToo movement and Southern European campaigns under slogans like “Ni una menos” and “Non una di meno” (Bonu Rosenkranz & Della Porta, 2025). These mobilizations, which originated in Latin America as part of the international feminist strike movement protesting femicide and rising rates of GBV (Gago, 2018), have significantly shaped public discourse and policy agendas. Through persistent efforts, feminist movements have successfully reframed GBV from a private or individualized matter into a collective political and social concern. These mobilizations have played a crucial role in shaping national and international legislation, leading to significant advances such as the ratification of the Istanbul Convention, heightened awareness of intersectional dimensions of GBV, and framing GBV as a structural and systemic issue rooted in patriarchy and capitalism.

However, at the same time GBV has increasingly become a contested and polarized field. A conservative backlash has emerged, with anti-gender campaigns challenging feminist interpretations of GBV and seeking to reverse recent policy gains or to obstruct anti-GBV legislation proposals (Montecchio 2024; Smrdelj & Kuhar, 2025). Notably, there have been persistent mobilizations against the Istanbul Convention in countries such as Poland, Slovenia, and Spain (Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017). In Turkey, anti-gender movements were instrumental in the government’s decision to withdraw from the Convention (Alnıaçık & Altan-Olcay, 2025). Conservative and far-right actors frequently portray gender equality policies, including measures addressing GBV, as Trojan horses for promoting so-called “gender ideology” (Paternotte & Kuhar, 2018; Verloo, 2018b). Across Western Europe, anti-feminist campaigns targeting the #MeToo movement, often spearheaded by men’s rights activists, have also gained traction and influence, highlighting the increasingly contentious landscape surrounding GBV policies and discourse.

In our DNA codebook, multiple concepts covered this policy issue area. To address broader, salient debates we included: violence against women and domestic violence acts; Istanbul Convention; child sexual abuse legislation; marital rape or sexual abuse legislation; rape or sexual consent legislation; GBV in the context of conflict/war. To delve into the particulars of these issues, we utilized more specific concepts, which were: programs for perpetrators; training of professionals; support services for survivors of GBV; restraining orders; safe custody and visitation rights for children; preventive imprisonment; prosecution based on women’s statement; consideration of aggravating circumstances; consideration of extenuating circumstances; spectacular punishment for GBV and child sexual abuse; mediation; resources for GBV policy making and implementation; resources for protecting child survivors of sexual abuse. In addition to these, there were country specific codes used in some instances.

⁴ This section is based on the work conducted within the thematic group on gender-based violence, drawing in particular on material from two draft papers. First, *Right-wing and anti-feminist attempts at co-optations in GBV debates* by Ayşe Alnıaçık, Özlem Altan-Olcay, Christina Grammatikopoulou, Andreas Beyer Gregersen, and second *The Contentious Field of Gender-Based Violence: Intra-Feminist Debates and Framing Ambiguities* by Giada Bonu Rosenkranz and Elin Peterson. It also incorporates material from the WP1 and WP2 fieldwork reports, particularly the DNA data prepared by Özlem Altan Olcay.

As indicated by our DNA findings, GBV was the most salient issue for multiple contexts. It was the one policy area whose concepts made it to all the top 20 lists drawn up for each country. However, while the top twenty debates of five countries (Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, and Spain) had at most two or three of these concepts, Turkey was an outlier in that the relevant concepts made it to the top 20 list eight times, and they occupied relatively high-ranking positions. The second runner up was Denmark’s list, which had four of the relevant concepts.

The predominant positioning of GBV related debates in the Turkish case, coincides with findings emerging from other data streams, which also ascertain the significance of debates around GBV related legislation, and the Istanbul Convention in the public domain.

Figure 5. Top 20 debated concepts, Turkish case

In the Danish case, there is an observed discrepancy between the results of the DNA and the position GBV occupies as a prominent theme in the interviews and the CFA results. However, given the fact that it still has more weight compared to the other national cases, the public domain appears to still be discussing what policies and legislation can effectively prevent and penalize GBV cases. It is also noteworthy that in all cases GBV discussions include debates on legislation defining what GBV is and how to address it. For example, in Denmark, the word “femicide” is not a separate legal category, with killings of women generally prosecuted under standard homicide laws. This has for a long time prevented an accurate assessment of the problem even though the existing data reveals that femicides make up about one-fifth of all homicide cases, with women as the majority of victims in this category.

Figure 6. Top 20 debated concepts, Danish case

For each case, we can interpret the presence of the GBV debates in diverse ways, ranging from strong disagreements about what constitutes domestic violence, violence against women, rape, and sexual abuse to how to penalize/prevent such acts. This is a policy area in which the feminist movements have historically achieved remarkable improvements in legislation.

Our further qualitative analysis in this thematic section is structured in two distinct parts based on two separate draft papers, with each part following the same tripartite structure focusing on, respectively, problem stream, policy stream, and politics stream. Both analyses centre on the role of ambiguities in policymaking processes. The first part addresses the cases of Denmark, Turkey, and Greece, where strong convergence across multiple research streams enables us to explore how anti-gender and anti-feminist actors frame GBV, particularly through the use of discursive ambiguity to undermine existing policies. The second part turns to Italy, Spain, and France, where GBV has been especially prominent in public debates and has often triggered strong feminist mobilizations. Here, the analysis considers how strategic ambiguities shape feminist efforts to influence the policy dimension.

In this way, we are able to develop a holistic approach whereby we combine a multiplicity of feminist and anti-gender framings of GBV as they emerge in different political contexts. The selected cases thus capture a wide spectrum: from contexts marked by entrenched anti-gender/anti-feminist discourses to those where feminist struggles have pushed GBV onto the policy agenda, highlighting both the enactment and, at times, the rollback of relevant policies.

Right-wing and anti-feminist attempts at co-optations in GBV debates

The first part of the analysis explores how anti-gender and anti-feminist actors frame the meaning and causes of GBV in three country cases: Denmark, Turkey, and Greece. It draws on data from the CFA, particularly analyses of activist documents and parliamentary debates produced within anti-gender and anti-feminist campaigns addressing GBV. These findings are further complemented by insights from interviews with anti-gender and anti-feminist actors conducted in the respective countries.

Through this material, our aim was to identify recurring frames and examine framing processes with particular attention to the role of ambiguity. Specifically, we studied how anti-gender and anti-feminist actors deploy discursive ambiguity regarding both the causes of GBV and its definition, in terms of what is “gender-based” and what counts as violence. We sought to unpack how these actors, as policy entrepreneurs, strategically employ ambiguity to undermine feminist demands and to obstruct or reverse legislative change aimed at preventing GBV.

In this context, ambiguity denotes a discursive strategy in which concepts and arguments have multiple meanings and this multiplicity is perpetuated indefinitely to strategic ends. In such instances, discursive ambiguity shows itself in two ways. First, anti-gender and anti-feminist actors contest the role of structural and normative gender inequalities as causal factors of GBV. Instead, they redirect attention to a wide range of alternative explanations - such as individual dispositions, drug or alcohol abuse, economic stress, or the race and ethnicity of perpetrators - arguing that these factors require greater scrutiny. This move generates uncertainty about what “really” causes violence and systematically downplays the role of gender. Second, discursive ambiguity is used to cast doubt on what constitutes violence. Here, actors claim that certain acts recognized in law (and by feminist campaigns) as violent are actually “normal” interactions, misunderstandings between partners, or behaviours occurring in dating contexts. By repeatedly questioning whether such acts should count as violence, they blur definitional boundaries and weaken feminist claims. In this way, anti-gender and anti-feminist actors sustain discursive ambiguity as a means of agenda denial: challenging feminist mobilizations for stronger

policy responses, obstructing effective implementation of GBV measures, and contributing to the rollback of existing legislation.

The three country cases were selected to represent a wide spectrum regarding both their regime structures, their political cultures and, more specifically, their GBV policy making. Denmark belongs to one end of such a spectrum with a parliamentary and multiparty democracy as well as a well-developed welfare state. GBV is not at the forefront of Danish politics, but new policies have been passed in recent years such as the 2020 consent-based rape law, provoking resistance from anti-feminist actors, particularly men's rights activists, in response to the #MeToo movement. Accordingly, our analysis focuses on the campaign opposing the #MeToo movement, where anti-feminist discourses sought to delegitimize feminist advances. In the Greek case, right-wing and anti-gender actors have capitalized on years of economic crisis and social distress by scapegoating both migrants, LGBTIQ+ communities, and feminists. This situation led to even more support to far right parties and extremist movements and subcultures. In relation to GBV, we analyse the campaign promoting the Shared Custody Act, which was the most drastic policy change, where successful lobbying by men's rights activists led to a change in the child custody law. In the Turkish case, the political context is characterized by a decade long democratic backsliding and, like Greece, increased scapegoating of feminists and LGBTIQ+ activists. These developments have also led to significant changes in GBV policy making, particularly with the successful campaign for the withdrawal of Turkey from the Istanbul Convention in 2021, despite large-scale protests from civil society. For this reason, our analysis concentrates on the debates surrounding the country's withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention.

In the following, we first focus on the problem stream by analysing discursive ambiguities in the framing of GBV across the country cases. In the policy stream, we discuss the role of such discursive ambiguities at a policy level which, in some cases, have led to the rolling back of GBV policies. Lastly, in the politics stream, we relate these findings to the broader political context and institutional structures in Denmark, Turkey, and Greece to reflect on the role of strategic ambiguity utilized by anti-feminist and anti-gender movements in different country contexts.

Problem stream

The analysis reveals how anti-gender and anti-feminist actors in all three countries cast doubt on the role of gender in GBV, by proposing instead other explanatory factors, considered to play a more important role in, for instance, domestic abuse. In Turkey and Greece, factors such as modernization and secularization, as well as alcohol and drugs, are often seen as main reasons leading to violence. In Denmark, the underlying causal factor is framed as a broken relation between men and women across society, leading also to more violence by women against men. In this manner, the possible role of gender norms and structures is not denied but rather placed in an ambiguous position as a minor causal factor next to numerous other factors explaining GBV.

Applying here the MSF approach, it can be argued that the discursive ambiguity effectively muddles the problem stream and contributes to agenda denial (Cobb & Ross, 1997, pp. 25-45) by discrediting feminist framings of GBV as an inherently structural issue based on gender inequalities and stereotypes.

Furthermore, the analysis shows how anti-gender and anti-feminist actors openly cast doubt on what counts or can be defined as violence and who should be considered victims without providing clear answers themselves. In Denmark, this type of ambiguous framing is evident among men's rights activists and other anti-feminist actors who, particularly in the context of debates on GBV following the #MeToo movement, question whether it is justifiable to classify "misunderstandings" in situations of dating

interactions and minor “violations” of boundaries as sexual harassment. It is especially the concept of “violation” (*krænkelse*) that is recurrently problematized as subjectivist and excessive:

“So, when we talk [about] MeToo, then there is goddammit no gender equality ... It is the women alone who decide what the violations and what the norms are in this area.” (Denmark, interview with anti-feminist actor, AG14)

Similarly, anti-feminist debaters in Turkey claim that the Istanbul Convention allows minor misunderstandings between husbands and wives to be conceived as domestic violence. At the same time, they also question whether the term violence is being diluted when it includes acts beyond physical violence. In this manner, they attempt to challenge the inclusion of psychological and economic violence in the definition of violence both in the Istanbul Convention and by feminist activists:

“The Istanbul Convention defines violence in physical, sexual, psychological and economic terms. In this conceptualization, physical violence and economic violence carry the same weight. Violence is not classified in terms of degrees of severity. It is reasonable to deploy serious and heavy sanctions in cases of physical violence. However, ... it is problematic that psychological and economic violence are treated in the same category.” (TURKEY_AG_SOCMOV_02)

In Greece, ambiguity around the definition of violence is taken to yet another level when men’s rights activists include men’s experiences of injustice in the family court system as forms of victimization, while simultaneously dismissing women’s reports of harassment as “exaggerations”. In this case, the gendered causal mechanisms are obfuscated with the inclusion of men as victims, and the definition of violence is being questioned by representing certain cases as mere “exaggeration”.

What is common across all three cases is that the very boundaries of what constitutes GBV and what defines an act as violent are systematically problematized by anti-gender and anti-feminist actors, without them offering alternative or consistent guidelines for delimiting acts of violence.

Policy stream

The two ways of discursively creating ambiguity concerning GBV, namely diverting attention from structural gender inequalities to alternative (individual) causes, and casting doubt on what is defined as violence, carry significant policy implications for identifying the underlying causes of GBV and for envisioning effective measures to address it. On the one hand, the anti-feminist and anti-gender actors are clear in terms of what they oppose and what they want to remove from the existing policy framework. In Turkey, this was the withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention, which happened in 2021. In Greece, it was the child custody legislation, which ended up being abolished the same year to be replaced with the Shared Custody Act, which was internationally criticized for failing to protect victims of GBV. In Denmark, the actors in question tried to abolish the consent-based rape law and currently prepare for an upcoming evaluation of the law scheduled for late-2025 to argue for its abolition. Yet, when requested to offer proposals for new forms of legislation on GBV, these actors in all three countries remain evasive, leaving it indefinite what these policies would be and how they would solve a problem, whose definition they do not agree with, anyway.

Seen together, the anti-feminist and anti-gender mobilizations, involving the employment of discursive ambiguities in the three countries, both hinder and muddle the policy initiatives proposed by feminist activists in the field of GBV. The major challenge for feminist movements is, therefore, to deliver effective rebuttals and critical analyses that provide clear insights on the area.

Politics stream

The three country cases also reveal that the role and significance of discursive ambiguity concerning GBV on a policy level is closely tied to the politics stream, i.e., the political context and opportunity structures that exist in these countries.

For instance, anti-feminist and anti-gender actors in both Denmark and Turkey emphasise that “simple misunderstandings” between men and women can become “misinterpreted” as GBV. However, this recurring theme is applied for different purposes and policy debates in the two countries: In the Danish case it serves to delegitimize the #MeToo movement and in the Turkish case to campaign against the Istanbul Convention.

The campaigns in the respective countries also reflect what is most often in focus in the public debate on GBV, with the #MeToo movement and sexual harassment being increasingly prominent themes in Denmark, while the Istanbul Convention and domestic violence have been widely debated in Turkey. In the Danish case, this is happening in a moment in time when right-wing discourses are becoming increasingly normalized and mainstreamed. Since 2017 and the rise of the #MeToo movement, there has been a surge in anti-feminist mobilizations with particularly men’s rights activists claiming that #MeToo have gone “too far”, and that policies such as the consent-based rape law should be rolled back. In the Turkish case, this is happening in an era largely defined by democratic backsliding with a shift from a parliamentary rule to a presidential regime. In Greece, the political opportunity structure changes can be seen in the electoral shift to the right. In this regressive political climate, men’s rights activists and anti-gender actors have leveraged their influence to successfully push forward their agenda about changing the child custody law. As a result, the 1983 custody law, which emphasized children’s best interests over parental rights, was replaced with a new law in 2021.

In all three cases, however, ambiguous discourses on GBV have contributed to the displacement of political focus from violence against women itself to other concerns in public debates. By obscuring both the causes and definitions of violence, anti-gender and anti-feminist actors adapt their arguments to prevailing political opportunity structures, whether by delegitimizing feminist gains, contesting international agreements, or advancing conservative legal reforms.

Intra-Feminist Debates and Framing Ambiguities in GBV

The second part of our analysis investigates how feminist movements in Italy, Spain, and France have shaped public understandings of GBV, while also highlighting internal debates and framing ambiguities. Drawing on interviews with feminist activists and political stakeholders, as well as CFA of movement documents and parliamentary debates, the analysis explores the diverse ways in which GBV is addressed within feminist discourses. Within feminist movements, significant debates arise over how to define GBV, its underlying causes, who bears responsibility, what can be identified as GBV, and which policy interventions should take priority. Such disputes reflect broader ideological divides concerning patriarchy, intersectionality, and the role of the state, and they deeply shape how feminist movements engage with institutions and seek to influence policy agendas. Thus, in this analysis, particular emphasis is placed on how feminist movements navigate internal diversity and external constraints, as they attempt to shape – or deliberately avoid – the policy dimension.

To navigate these tensions, feminist actors frequently employ “strategic ambiguity” as a deliberate flexibility in framing to maintain broad coalitions, secure institutional support, or avoid alienating potential allies, particularly in the policy arena. While such ambiguity can facilitate policy influence by presenting GBV in terms palatable to institutions, it can also marginalize more radical or intersectional perspectives, such as those focusing on racialized women, migrants, sex workers, or trans people. Consequently, institutional uptake frequently rewards simplified framings, leaving complex and

intersectional experiences underrepresented in policy debates. The analysis explores how these framing struggles impact the translation of feminist claims into policy in Italy, Spain, and France, highlighting framing as both a site of contestation and a tool for political influence.

Italy, Spain, and France have been selected as key sites for analysis because these countries have seen major feminist mobilizations around GBV over the past decade, driving mass protests and marches, launching influential campaigns, and generating rich and varied movement material. Yet, the country cases present contrasting models of institutionalization and legal frameworks. Spain has developed a robust legal framework on GBV and sexual consent, complemented by highly visible feminist activism. Mass demonstrations, protests after high-profile cases, and viral social media campaigns have gone hand in hand with legal advances, largely because feminist actors have consistently engaged institutions and pressed for state-led solutions. In contrast, Italy shows a less consolidated institutional response. While feminist activism has been longstanding, legal reforms have been slower and often focused on punitive measures. Since 2016, the Non Una di Meno (NUDM) movement has renewed mobilization, promoting intersectional and community-based solutions that signal scepticism toward state-led strategies. France occupies a middle ground between the Spanish and Italian trajectories. While feminist movements have been highly visible and GBV has gained public attention through high-profile cases, institutional responses have remained uneven and contested. Taken together, these variations provide a valuable basis for comparison, showing how contrasting models of institutionalization and legal frameworks shape the possibilities for feminist influence on GBV policy.

As with the previous analysis, in the problem stream, we will first focus on how GBV is defined and addressed by the feminist movements in Italy, Spain, and France. Thereafter, in relation to the policy stream and the politics stream, we connect these findings to the political cultures, policy initiatives and changes, as well as the overall relation between the feminist movements and the state in the three country cases.

Problem stream

Across the three countries, feminist movements largely agree that GBV is a structural problem rooted in patriarchy and reinforced by intersecting systems of oppression, such as capitalism, racism, and heteronormativity. This consensus is visible in movement documents and interviews, where GBV is portrayed as multifaceted, extending beyond physical or sexual violence to include economic, institutional, and cultural forms of harm. Activists consistently emphasize the systemic nature of violence, describing it as interwoven into social institutions, public spaces, and private relationships. This appears, for instance, particularly clearly in the #NousToutes movement in France:

“In 2018, we chose to have a very simple way of communicating struggles (...) we had a pie chart that said “Who has the responsibility in a rape case? The size of the skirt 0%, Patriarchat 100%”
(France, interview with feminist activist, FA)

However, there are significant divergences within feminist movements on how GBV should be defined and addressed. One axis of contention concerns intersectionality. In the three countries, many grassroots feminists frame GBV as connected to multiple forms of oppression, highlighting the unique vulnerabilities of migrants, racialized women, LGBTIQ+ people, and economically vulnerable women. Intersectionality is thus framed not only as an analytical tool but as a transformative political strategy. Yet, tensions emerge over how far intersectional analysis should extend, especially when it disrupts traditional feminist categories centred on cisgender women. In Italy, NUDM criticizes the tendency of institutional policies to avoid naming specific axes of oppression, leading to a “flattening of difference”:

“Campaigns against bullying in schools often take on neutral connotations, as if they were afraid to name the differences of gender, race, class, and sexual orientation that connote oppression.”
(ITALY_FEM_SOCMOV)

In Spain, written feminist materials vary in their embrace of intersectionality. Some key documents, like those tied to the 7N State March and sexual violence protests, focus primarily on women as a broad category, while others, such as those from the 8M feminist strikes, explicitly integrate intersectional perspectives. Institutional actors often stick to binary gender definitions to secure broad consensus, but grassroots feminist voices push back, calling for a deeper critique of gender roles and the systems that exploit differences.

Compared to this ambivalence in Spain, the French case shows a more explicit polarization around intersectionality. For one part of the feminist movement, intersectionality has become a central rallying point, particularly in struggles against femonationalism (Jourde, 2025), while for others it marks a dividing line with associations that continue to defend a universalist framework:

“[Intersectionality] is a word that is clearly inscribed now [in our status], but it’s one of the reasons that made us fall out with certain feminist associations that claim to be ‘universalist’, that oppose universalism and intersectionality. However, at the Planning Familial, we have argued that to defend universal rights, you also need an intersectional approach.” (France, interview with feminist activist, FA)

Two particularly divisive topics are trans inclusion and sex work. Gender-critical feminists in the three countries resist including trans women in GBV frameworks, arguing that violence should be framed specifically as male violence against women. They view trans inclusion as undermining the category of “woman” and diluting feminist struggles. This has produced ontological fractures within feminist movements, with some activists accusing trans-inclusive feminism of playing into the hands of patriarchy. In France, for instance, this divide became particularly visible around the definition of femicides and who should be counted as victims. In 2022, the large feminist collective #NousToutes stopped relaying statistics produced by another collective (Féminicides par compagnon ou ex) because they included only cisgender women. Instead #NousToutes launched its own count in partnership with intersectional alliances involving trans-rights, sex-workers’ rights, disabled feminists, and anti-HIV groups. This emblematic case illustrates the persistent divides between feminist collectives over how GBV is defined and whose experiences are recognized.

Sex work similarly divides movements. Gender-critical feminists often frame prostitution as inherently violent and exploitative, opposing its legalization. Others argue for recognizing sex work as labour and demand protections for sex workers. In Spain, these disputes have even resulted in separate feminist demonstrations on March 8th in some cities, highlighting deep internal fractures:

“The feminist coordinator of Valencia, which is a platform, let’s say, formed by various organisations, including political parties and unions. And we wanted to dissociate ourselves from their call, because among other things, there are some points on which we do not agree, that also generate a lot of unrest and exclusion of the comrades that are in our Assembly, such as trans people or sex workers. So, we decided to generate an alternative call in which all these people would fit (...) Before we used to call for the same demonstration, but two years ago, since they had a super abolitionist head banner, we decided to generate another call.” (Spain, interview with feminist activist, FA18)

These findings reveal that feminist framings of GBV are neither monolithic nor static but are strategically negotiated and context-dependent. Ambiguity in framing GBV allows diverse groups to collaborate

without fully resolving ideological differences, serving as both a resource for unity around major policy issues and a risk of silencing marginalized voices, like trans people and sex workers. Findings also show that internal conflicts are integral, rather than detrimental, to feminist politics, especially amid growing anti-gender mobilizations and democratic challenges. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for comprehending how feminist movements respond to both external opposition and internal diversity in times of social and political transformation.

Policy stream

A major difference between the three countries in question lies in their respective feminist movements' relationships with the state. In Italy, relationship of the feminist movement with the state is largely ambivalent and movements tend to keep a critical distance from institutions. Despite this scepticism, Italian feminists have achieved important policy gains, such as the legal recognition of femicide, and have occasionally collaborated with institutional actors, particularly in providing services for survivors amid chronic underfunding of anti-violence centres. Overall, however, the movement prioritizes autonomy and broader structural transformation over purely legal reforms. They often advocate for transformative justice and community-based alternatives over punitive responses, reflecting a distrust of state mechanisms and a desire to maintain movement autonomy.

“We don’t focus too much on the legislative point of view because laws usually change when society changes. We don’t think that changing the law first and then finding that society hasn’t changed is the best way to start.” (Italy, interview with feminist activist, FA15)

Consistent with this perspective, the movement largely pursues indirect influence, aiming to drive change through external pressure instead of relying on formal lobbying or close cooperation with political institutions. This approach of conflictual engagement enables activists to apply pressure while maintaining independence and resisting full absorption into institutional structures.

By contrast, in Spain, feminist actors actively engage with institutions and frame GBV as a state responsibility, pushing for legal reforms and comprehensive state interventions. Spanish feminists have secured major advances like the “Only Yes Is Yes” law and the State Pact Against Gender Violence. They see the state as a crucial actor in eliminating GBV and demand public funding, legal protections, and policy implementation. This engagement has yielded significant legislative victories but has also led to criticism from more radical factions, who worry about co-optation and the over-reliance on punitive, carceral solutions.

“Not just focusing on punishment, but also providing tools, spaces for reflection, and support - so it doesn’t happen again, right? So that aggressors also go through a process and change is possible - not just punishment and that’s it.” (Spain, interview with feminist activist, FA17)

As an interesting point of comparison, France occupies a middle ground between Spain and Italy, with attempts by feminist movements to collaborate with the state on policy making accompanied by weak results but also an increasing lack of trust in the government to effectively support the fight against GBV. Like Spain, French feminist movements have placed strong faith in the power of public action, yet - similar to Italy, though less intensely - they often find themselves in a conflictual relationship with institutions. Feminist actors combine confrontational strategies, such as mass demonstrations on and around 25 November, with lobbying and awareness-raising efforts directed at policymakers. One of the major institutionalized feminist organizations, Planning Familial, regularly participates in policy discussions and was heavily involved in the 2019 National Gathering on Domestic Violence, while at the same time remaining critical of the limited achievements of government policy on women’s rights. Such large

associations also play a mediating role, relaying concerns raised by smaller, less connected groups. As one feminist actor from Planning Familial noted:

“It is true that in Planning Familial we are always in contact with politicians, because the objective is also to influence policies and make them evolve.” (France, interview with feminist activist, FA)

Smaller feminist organizations tend to welcome opportunities to engage in dialogue with institutions. One group working against cyber-harassment described how it actively sought to be heard by policy-makers and was consulted on two different laws, including legislation criminalizing the dissemination of intimate content. As one representative recalled:

“I think we had small victories at the beginning. Because at the beginning the politicians knew so little about the subject that they really needed to have our insight, and they listened to us.” (France, interview with feminist activist, FA)

Despite their different relationships with institutions in the policymaking process, feminists in the three countries share concerns over the limitations of punitive approaches and advocate for intersectional, community-based solutions beyond carceral measures.

Politics stream

As already emphasized, a significant dimension of the politics stream in Italy, Spain, and France is the feminist movements' relations to the political system and the state. Spain has developed a robust legal framework, exemplified by the Organic Law 1/2004 on Comprehensive Protection Measures Against Gender Violence, the ratification of the Istanbul Convention in 2014, the State Pact against Gender Violence (2017-present), and the 2022 “Only Yes Is Yes” law, which redefined sexual consent and expanded victim protections. Feminist activism in Spain has been highly visible through events like the 7N State March in 2015 and 2016, widespread protests following high-profile cases such as “La Manada”, gang rape, and viral hashtags like #YoSíTeCreo (“I believe you”) and #NoEsAbusoEsViolación (“It’s not abuse, it’s rape”).

Conversely, in Italy, the institutional response has been less consolidated and more uneven. Feminist activism has been ongoing since the 1970s, starting with the creation of women’s shelters and anti-violence centres and campaigns reframing violence as a political issue. Legal reforms have progressed more slowly, with milestones like Law 66/1996 redefining sexual violence as a crime against the person. Italy ratified the Istanbul Convention in 2013, but subsequent measures - such as the 2019 “Codice Rosso” law - have largely focused on punitive tools and emergency mechanisms. The politics stream was significantly reshaped by the emergence of the NUDM movement in 2016, which revitalized feminist mobilization while expressing scepticism toward state interventions. Instead, it has promoted alternative, community-driven solutions, most notably the *Piano Femminista Contro la Violenza*, emphasizing intersectionality and non-punitive approaches.

In France, feminist movements have expanded significantly over the past decade, addressing a wide range of issues within French society (Jourde, 2025). This led some scholars to characterize the 2010s as a period of “success” for feminism (Viennot & Wiels, 2019). GBV re-emerged at the forefront of mobilizations as early as 2011, when two high-profile cases of sexual violence involving political figures - the Strauss-Kahn and Baupin cases - sparked national debate. Legal instruments introduced thereafter only partially improved protections against sexist and sexual violence. Despite President Emmanuel Macron presenting himself as a “feminist candidate” in 2017 and launching a major initiative with the 2019 National Gathering on Domestic Violence, the outcomes of these measures for women’s rights

remain highly contested (Lhote-Fernandes, 2022; Pierre-Brossolette et al., 2023). Moreover, the increased visibility of violence against women has also enabled the instrumentalization of feminist issues by ethno-nationalist movements, which use the language of gender equality to advance xenophobic agendas (Farris, 2017).

Feminist movements in all three countries increasingly face GBV as a polarized and contested field in politics with increased resistance from anti-feminist and anti-gender actors, as testified from the previous comparative analysis. Yet, the movements can also draw on historical experiences of successfully putting GBV on the political agenda, and despite internal conflicts and ambiguous discourses, feminist activism has contributed to significant policy gains in recent years and changed public discourse by emphasizing GBV as a structural issue. What the long-term cultural changes of such advances might be remains to be seen.

Main Takeaways

Over recent decades, feminist mobilizations across Europe have successfully contributed to reframe GBV as a political and systemic issue rather than a private matter. Through strategic framing, activists have defined GBV as rooted in patriarchy and intersecting systems like capitalism and racism, influencing significant legal advances such as the Istanbul Convention and consent-based sexual violence laws in Spain and Denmark. However, the policy field has become increasingly polarized as anti-gender actors contest these framings and seek to reverse policy gains. Ongoing disputes, both within feminist movements and between feminist and anti-gender actors, continue to shape how feminist demands translate into policy.

Our analysis shows that although feminist movements have effectively influenced the problem stream by redefining GBV as structural and systemic, the policy stream remains contested, with diverging solutions ranging from punitive measures to transformative justice. In Spain, strong institutional engagement has yielded legal reforms, whereas in Italy and France, feminist movements maintain rather “conflictual engagement” than close collaboration with the state. These differences shape distinct policy windows and institutional pathways for reform. Our findings show that strategic ambiguity is a crucial tool for feminist movements, helping to maintain broad coalitions and institutional traction. However, while ambiguity unites diverse actors under broad frames, it risks marginalizing radical or intersectional perspectives. This tension highlights how framing processes influence which definitions and policy solutions gain legitimacy within institutional arenas.

Anti-gender actors in countries like Turkey, Greece, and Denmark increasingly exploit discursive ambiguity to undermine feminist framings of GBV. By casting doubt on gender norms as root causes or questioning what counts as violence, they fragment the problem stream and obstruct feminist policy agendas. For instance, in Denmark, men’s right activists challenge the concept of “violence”, describing it as overly subjective and misused in relation to #MeToo. In Turkey and Greece, critics argue that laws like the Istanbul Convention criminalize minor marital conflicts, fuelling narratives that feminist laws threaten traditional family structures. Such reframing shifts GBV from a structural issue to an individualized or moral concern, undermining feminist calls for systemic change. The discursive ambiguity behind this reframing enables the anti-feminist and anti-gender actors to speak against feminist positions without pinpointing their own. And because they do not explicitly define their position, they can appear more moderate even though the demands to dismantle existing legal frameworks suggest far-reaching political goals around gender norms and policies. This creates a fragmented problem stream, where competing interpretations hinder agenda-setting and reduce the clarity necessary for decisive policy action. Anti-gender actors block or delay the policy windows of opportunity by challenging feminist

problem definitions and offering alternative narratives, sometimes successfully blocking or reversing policy changes.

2.4.3. Health and Reproductive Rights⁵

Reproductive rights have long been at the focus of feminist activism and central to struggles for bodily autonomy, health and gender equality. Advances in reproductive rights must be understood within the context of growing global interdependence and the institutionalization of women's demands at the international level since the 1990s. Key United Nations conferences in Cairo and Beijing during that decade firmly embedded reproductive rights within human rights frameworks, shaping global discourse and generating political commitments to safeguard women's reproductive health and freedom. These developments contributed significantly to the global recognition of gender equality and sexual and reproductive rights. However, progress has been uneven, often shaped by compromises and ongoing tensions with religious and pronatalist forces (Rebouché, 2016, p. 768).

Over the past decade, reproductive rights, particularly the right to abortion, have remained deeply contested worldwide (Ferre, 2003; Rebouché, 2016). While the broader trend has favoured the legalization and protection of abortion rights, with notable advances like France's 2024 constitutional amendment enshrining the right to abortion, other countries have experienced significant setbacks. In countries like Poland, restrictive laws have curtailed access (Muszel & Piotrowski, 2025), while even countries with comparatively liberal frameworks, such as Italy and Slovenia, face persistent challenges to ensuring effective reproductive rights (Barone et al., 2025; Lavizzari, Barone & Bonu Rosenkranz, 2025; Markelj & Pajnik, 2025). In cases such as Turkey, political actors have proposed abortion bans but to be thwarted by feminist mobilization (Altan-Olcay & Alnıaçık, 2025). These obstacles are driven in part by growing anti-abortion mobilizations and the broader anti-gender movement, which opposes sexual and reproductive rights under the rhetoric of resisting so-called "gender ideology". Reproductive rights, historically central to anti-gender discourse, remain at the forefront of these cultural and political battles (Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017, p. 9; Smrdelj & Kuhar 2025). Across many contexts, anti-gender actors have succeeded in rolling back policies, fuelling conservative backlash, and introducing procedural barriers that limit practical access to abortion. As a result, reproductive rights continue to symbolize the contested terrain where feminist advocacy meets conservative resistance, reflecting deeper struggles over democracy and gender equality.

Reproductive rights directly intersect with deeply held beliefs about morality, religion, and national identity, making them particularly susceptible to political instrumentalization. This thematic section focuses specifically on anti-gender mobilizations because they have become key actors in shaping reproductive rights policies, deploying powerful frames and strategic narratives that threaten to erode existing legal protections and restrict practical access to reproductive health services across Europe.

As our DNA data indicates, one of the most debated reproductive rights is the right to abortion. In the codebook, the policy issue area of health and reproductive rights was coded through the following concepts: access to abortion; access to contraception; medically assisted reproductive rights; access to surrogacy; privacy rights in pregnancy; access to affordable and non-discriminatory sexual and reproductive health care services; and access to affordable menstrual products. In some cases, additional country-specific codes were also applied. Reflecting broader contestations over reproductive rights, the DNA findings show that this policy area did not consistently rank among the top twenty most salient issues across countries. However, where it did appear, the debate was primarily centred on

⁵ This section is based on the work conducted within the thematic group on health and reproductive rights, drawing in particular on material from the draft paper *Demographic winter as an exemplification of the diffusion of anti-gender discourses between grassroots movements and policymakers* by Grzegorz Piotrowski, Magdalena Muszel, Christina Grammatikopoulou, Leja Markelj and Rok Smrdelj. It also incorporates material from the WP1 and WP2 fieldwork reports, particularly the DNA data prepared by Özlem Altan Olcay.

access to abortion. Aggregated data across countries confirms that abortion was among the most controversial topics, revealing deep societal divides over women’s right to access it. This trend was especially pronounced in Italy, Poland, and Slovenia, where other aspects of reproductive rights also appeared more frequently compared to other countries. Moreover, the intensity of the abortion debate in Poland and Slovenia numerically contributed to the overall degree of controversy captured in the aggregate data.

These findings reveal to us, once again, the potential vulnerability of the legislative and discursive achievements of feminist movements (not just in these particular cases, but also across the world) when it comes to reproductive rights. Given the expanding claims of protecting children and families by anti-gender activists (Kuhar et al., forthcoming) and the expanding space public debates on “demographic winter” occupy, this is a policy area on which there is need for more focus to protect and facilitate women’s rights to make decisions about reproduction freely.

Figure 7. Top 20 debated concepts, Italian case

Figure 8. Top 20 debated concepts, Polish case

Figure 9. Top 20 debated concepts, Slovenian case

To explore this trend further, we focused on the qualitative analysis of anti-gender discourse on reproductive rights in three country cases: Poland, Slovenia, and Greece. There is a notable convergence between the DNA and CFA data on the prominence of abortion debates in both the Polish and Slovenian contexts. While the DNA findings identify Italy as a top contender in terms of national newspaper coverage, particularly regarding abortion, the CFA data from Greece offers deeper insights into concrete mobilizations and policy disputes during the observed period. Therefore, we selected Greece as the third case in order to ensure a more robust and empirically grounded analysis of anti-gender discourse related to reproductive rights.

The analysis in the rest of the section explores the deployment of the discourse on “demographic winter”, with the main argument on declining birth rates posing existential threats to economies, cultures, and national survival. The demographic winter is today among the most prominent discourses of the anti-gender movements in their opposition to reproductive rights. Drawing on empirical material from the CFA of anti-gender activist documents and parliamentary debates revolving around reproductive rights, we investigate - through a comparative lens - how “demographic winter” narratives travel from civil society into policymaking. Specifically, we examine how this discourse is strategically employed both by movement actors and by political representatives who act as key policy entrepreneurs in advancing anti-gender agendas.

Poland, Slovenia and Greece were chosen as critical case studies where nationalist and religious narratives link national identity to natalism and family values. Each country illustrates unique, yet interlinked dynamics where declining fertility rates, nationalist discourses, and religious conservatism converge to frame reproductive autonomy as a threat to national survival. In all three contexts, declining birth rates and ethnonationalist discourses have fuelled anti-gender mobilizations that frame reproductive autonomy, particularly abortion, as a threat to the nation. While Poland exemplifies the most restrictive legal measures, Slovenia and Greece illustrate how similar discourses circulate within institutions and public debates, despite differing legal frameworks. In Slovenia, reproductive rights have been constitutionally protected since the 1974 Yugoslav Constitution, whereas in Greece, abortion has been legal under Law 1609/1986 since its adoption in 1986. Together, these cases provide a comparative lens to explore how demographic winter narratives, as part of broader anti-gender discourse, migrate from civil society into parliamentary debates and policymaking, reframing reproductive rights as a matter of national security,

with policy entrepreneurs playing a key role in forging transversal alliances and aligning diverse interests and frames within these processes.

In the following sections, we begin by unpacking the problem stream, examining how anti-gender actors have articulated and constructed demographic winter as the central issue in debates on reproductive rights. In the policy stream, we turn to the articulation of solutions and the concrete policy proposals debated in parliaments, analysing how the narratives of demographic winter are translated into formal policy language and legal frameworks. Finally, in the political stream, we reflect on the broader political climate that enables anti-gender rhetoric to gain traction and creates the conditions for the advancement of restrictive reproductive policies.

Problem stream

Although opposition to reproductive rights has been historically present in Poland, Slovenia, and Greece, the recent backlash has intensified with the rise of anti-gender movements, including family associations, religious groups, and pro-life initiatives in Slovenia (e.g., 40 Days for Life, March for Life); men's rights groups and far-right parties such as the Spartiates in Greece, with the ruling New Democracy party also adopting anti-gender discourse; and in Poland, conservative organizations like Ordo Iuris and Pro–Prawo do Życia, closely allied with the conservative-populist Law and Justice party. In all three country cases, anti-gender movements have successfully positioned reproductive rights within the framework of national survival. Central to their strategy is the notion of a “demographic winter,” a metaphor that reimagines declining birth rates not merely as a demographic concern but as an existential threat to the nation. The demographic winter discourse often overlaps with populist concept of a “besieged fortress” (Ziółkowski, 2022), combining fears of depopulation with anxieties about immigration. Declining birth rates are attributed not to socio-economic factors but to moral decay caused by gender equality and reproductive freedom. This logic reimagines gender rights as threats, requiring corrective policies that enforce traditional gender roles and heterosexual family models. Anti-gender actors exploit demographic fears to push restrictive laws on abortion, contraception, and sex education, casting reproductive rights as civic duties necessary for national preservation.

However, the way this narrative unfolds in each country reflects distinct political cultures, historical trajectories and ideological landscapes. In Slovenia, demographic decline is woven into a broader narrative of moral crisis. Anti-gender actors frame abortion and contraception as instruments of a pervasive “culture of death” (Pajnik, Markelj & Humer, forthcoming). They argue that reproductive autonomy leads to psychological harm for women and undermines the future of the Slovenian nation. An important marker within this discourse is the figure of the “unborn child”, which emphasizes the civil rights of unborn citizens and has long been part of the discursive repertoire of anti-choice groups globally (Cannold, 2002) The “unborn child” is personalized, portrayed as a lost citizen whose absence symbolizes both moral and demographic decay. Parliamentary debates echo these themes, revealing how the discourse has seeped into institutional language. Political figures invoke positioning motherhood as a civic duty critical to preserving national identity.

“Cardinal Rode won the Bob of the Year award a few years ago when he said that love for the nation begins in bed. And there is great truth in that saying. We all know that birth rates, demography, is a problem in Slovenia. It used to be that every woman should have three children, one for herself, one for her father and one for her country. Now we have 1.5 or fewer children per woman (...) We must do something. Or are we just going to wait for the Slovenian nation to die out?” (SLOVENIA_AG_PD_07)

In Greece, demographic discourse is profoundly shaped by ethnonationalism. Here, declining fertility is narrated as a threat not just to population numbers, but to the continuity of a culturally and racially defined Greek identity. In this narrative, the “demographic winter” is transformed into a conspiracy of “great replacement” (Camus, 2012), where low birth rates combined with migration are portrayed as leading to the replacement of the local population by migrants: *“Many couples no longer have children, for financial reasons. Thus, they resort to abortions, the easy solution, instead of feeling blessed and raising their children, even with fewer goods. In a few years there will be no Greeks left. The replacement has already begun”* (Vlachou, 2017).

The ideological framework of Hellenism, which fuses notions of racial purity and gendered citizenship, further underpins pronatalist campaigns that frame low birth rates as a “national plague” (Brysk & Yang, 2023) and attribute this decline to LGBTIQ+ rights, immigration, and feminism. This narrative reinforces an ideal of the traditional family while excluding those who deviate from patriarchal and heteronormative roles. While feminist resistance has pushed back against overtly sexist or pseudo-scientific narratives, pronatalist sentiment remains strong.

Poland presents perhaps the most aggressive articulation of demographic anxiety. The narrative here centres explicitly on cultural and moral decline, blamed on feminism, secularism, and liberal Western values. Right-wing politicians and conservative media consistently portray declining fertility as the biological price of women’s emancipation and modern lifestyles. Prominent figures have made inflammatory statements accusing young women of sacrificing motherhood in pursuit of careers and pleasure. These views depict feminism as a civilizational threat, recasting demographic decline as the outcome of ideological warfare.

“Today, the problem is simply a fear - and selfishness- driven aversion to having children. This applies primarily to women who succumb to the mentality prevalent in pop culture, in which work and professional success are the main goals in life for women. As it turns out, this attitude has a significant impact on fertility, as women’s aspirations are primarily related to their professional careers.” (POLAND_AG_SOCMOV_11)

Across all three cases, the depiction of women as essential reproducers of the nation appears as an important aspect, whose fertility is framed as a ‘civic duty tied to national survival’. This is particularly visible in the Greek case, where maternal role is deeply embedded within an ethnonationalist framework. Pronatalist narratives target Greek women explicitly, positioning their fertility as essential for safeguarding Hellenic identity. Migrant women, Roma communities, and other minorities are systematically excluded from this vision. Across all contexts, these narratives are not only cultural but deeply political, mobilised by policy entrepreneurs who channel them into legislative debates, institutional agendas, and cross-sector alliances, thereby shaping both policy framing and concrete measures on family, migration, and reproductive rights.

Policy stream

Despite national differences, all three countries share a common prognostic strategy: translating demographic anxieties into concrete policy proposals. Importantly, these narratives have moved from civil society into state institutions, shaping national policy on reproductive rights in some countries. The “demographic winter” narrative appears both in discussions surrounding existing family policies designed to bolster birth rates and in concrete policy proposals advanced by anti-gender actors during parliamentary debates.

Among the three cases, Poland stands out as a distinct case of implementation of regressive policies in the field of reproductive rights. In Poland, policy interventions are far more robust and legally binding

in comparison to Slovenia and Greece, where policy implications hold symbolic meaning but did not (yet) impact the existing legal frameworks. Programs like “Family 500+” (Ministry of Family, Labour and Social Policy, Republic of Poland, 2017) provide financial incentives for childbirth, explicitly framed as investments in national strength:

“What matters in life is family, it’s children—this is not a cost, it’s an investment. Children and family are the foundation of Poland and our future. This is our greatest challenge today.” (POLAND_AG_PD_06)

Yet alongside economic policies, there are harsh legal restrictions: the 2020 Constitutional Tribunal ruling effectively banning abortion on foetal impairment grounds exemplifies how moral discourse is codified into law. Pronatalist policy is thus enforced through both financial incentives and punitive legal measures.

In contrast, while legal frameworks on reproductive rights remain largely intact in both Slovenia and Greece, the proposed policy solutions increasingly reflect anti-gender narratives that promote pronatalism and reinforce traditional gender roles. In Slovenia, policy solutions blend moral appeals with economic incentives. Anti-gender actors advocate subsidies for families, early employment stability for young couples, and social benefits to encourage childbearing. Calls for institutional measures, such as the reestablishment of the Office for Demography, highlight efforts to embed pronatalist ideology into state structures:

“At a time when Slovenia is facing low birth rates and an aging population, the government abolished the only institution in our country that sought to raise fertility and create conditions enabling families to choose to have children. Therefore, we call on Prime Minister Robert Golob to place children and families at the centre of his policies and to re-establish the Office for Demography. Children and families are the only solution to Slovenia’s health, social, pension, and economic problems.” (SLOVENIA_AG_SOCMOV_06)

Notably, proposals often combine neoliberal economic logic, treating children and families as future economic assets, with conservative moral values that elevate motherhood as a civic obligation.

In Greece, recent policy measures are embedded within a strongly ethnonationalist framework. The dissolution of gender equality institutions and their replacement with family-oriented bodies, most notably the substitution of the Secretariat for Gender Equality with a “Ministry of Social Cohesion and Family”, signal a systematic redirection of state resources toward pronatalist goals. Within this context, reproductive rights are increasingly politicized: abortion is reframed not as a matter of health and individual autonomy but as a question of democracy and national survival. Calls by members of parliament for a referendum to restrict abortion law further exemplify this shift. Moreover, events like “Family Pride” marches and the institutional support for fertility conferences highlight how government rhetoric has aligned with anti-gender actors.

Politics stream

Across Poland, Slovenia, and Greece, the political stream has become increasingly fertile ground for the institutionalization of anti-gender discourses, particularly those framing reproductive autonomy as a threat to national survival. In each country, demographic anxieties have been strategically leveraged by political elites, enabling the migration of anti-gender narratives from civil society into formal policymaking arenas.

In Poland, the convergence between anti-gender activism and state policy has reached its most pronounced form. Conservative-populist actors have long instrumentalized demographic fears to justify

some of the harshest abortion restrictions in Europe. The 2020 Constitutional Tribunal ruling, which effectively eliminated access to abortion in cases of foetal anomaly, marked a high point in the institutionalization of anti-gender discourse. Political leaders openly framed abortion as a threat to national continuity and Christian civilization, shifting reproductive rights debates from a health and autonomy perspective to one rooted in ethno-nationalist moralism. State policies such as the “Family 500+” child benefit program further reinforce traditional gender roles by incentivizing fertility as a patriotic duty. Furthermore, in Poland, the Church’s influence remains strong. Women are thus positioned as reproducers of both faith and nation, subjected to intense scrutiny and moral expectations.

“If a woman does not fulfil herself physically as a mother, she is then called to spiritual motherhood, to dedicate herself to God and to others.” (POLAND_AG_SOCMOV_12)

In Slovenia, despite constitutional protections for reproductive rights, anti-gender actors influence political debates by aligning with conservative and right-wing parties. Through restrictive policy proposals, public demonstrations, and rhetorical campaigns such as the annual March for Life, these actors have mainstreamed narratives that link reproductive rights, particularly abortion, to national decline. Right-wing parties have increasingly adopted this framing, embedding it into legislative proposals and public discourse, even in the absence of major legal reforms.

In Greece, the politics stream has been shaped by a decade of economic crisis, the rise of right-wing populist actors, and the deepening of cultural conservatism. Importantly, the Greek state is deeply entangled with the Orthodox Church, whose privileged position is constitutionally protected. The absence of a clear separation between church and state means that the Orthodox Church plays a significant role in shaping public debates and policy positions on gender issues. Even when government and religious leaders diverge, political authorities often seek acknowledgment from the Church, ensuring its continued influence in both the media and governance. These conditions have allowed anti-gender rhetoric to flourish, with far-right parties directly attacking abortion rights, while the ruling New Democracy party has incorporated elements of anti-gender discourse into its governance strategy. This has included symbolic institutional changes, such as replacing the Secretariat for Gender Equality with a “Ministry of Social Cohesion and Family”, reinforcing traditional gender roles under the guise of national unity. Participation in conferences on fertility and pronatalist policies reflects a femonationalist approach that instrumentalizes women’s bodies for demographic objectives, while strong ethnonationalist and Orthodox narratives link falling fertility to national decline, supporting exclusionary family policies.

Main Takeaways

The notion of “demographic winter” functions as a strategic frame in anti-gender mobilizations, reframing reproductive rights as threats to national survival. While Slovenia, Greece, and Poland deploy similar demographic narratives, significant differences shape how these narratives play out in different national contexts. Through the lens of problem stream, we show that Slovenian discourse emphasizes moral and emotional appeals relying on cultural traditionalism, Greece intertwines reproductive policy with ethnonationalism, and Poland frames demographic concerns as a moral war against feminism and liberalism, with political actors attributing low fertility not to economic conditions but to cultural degeneration and women’s pursuit of independence.

Collectively, these country cases illustrate how the “demographic winter” narrative operates as a versatile ideological tool, which is also translated into concrete policy proposals in the policy stream. In Poland, this has led to legally binding restrictions, including one of the most severe abortion regimes in Europe. Here, pronatalist policy is implemented through both financial incentives and punitive legal reforms, institutionalizing a governance model rooted in nationalist and Catholic moralism.

In the politics stream, all three countries show how demographic fears have been effectively leveraged by political elites to mainstream anti-gender discourse. This analysis shows how anti-gender actors, particularly in Polish case, exploit windows of opportunity, often during political turbulence or societal crises, to insert the frames into the policy debates, transforming ideological claims into institutionalized law. In this regard, demographic anxiety becomes a powerful indicator in the problem stream, drawing political and public attention. Anti-gender movements and conservative political elites act as policy entrepreneurs, coupling this problem with restrictive policy proposals in the policy stream, such as abortion bans or pronatalist incentives, and leveraging shifts in the political stream fuelled by rising nationalism and populism. In this sense, it is possible to speak of the alignment of the three streams (problem, policy, politics). In contrast, in Slovenia and Greece, although proposed policy solutions increasingly incorporate anti-gender ideologies, the legal frameworks for reproductive rights remain formally intact. This indicates that the three streams have not yet converged. In Slovenia, this can be attributed to constitutional protections for reproductive rights, which pose significant obstacles to overturning these provisions and lead political decision-makers to adopt a cautious approach (Barone et al., 2025). In Greece, anti-abortion campaigns have failed in achieving concrete policy changes, possibly because they triggered established reflexes within mainstream politics and civil society, rooted in how Greeks perceive themselves as part of contemporary European democracy (Kioupiolis, 2025a).

Taken together, these findings show that anti-gender discourse functions not only as cultural backlash but as a strategic mode of governance, producing policies, reshaping institutions, and redefining rights within broader nationalist and authoritarian projects. At the same time, the findings highlight the importance of feminist strategies that safeguard access to abortion through grassroots initiatives (Barone et al., 2025; Lavizzari, Barone, & Bonu Rosenkranz, 2025; Muszel, 2025), while also raising pressing questions about how such resistance can be sustained amid structural transformations and effectively translated into lasting policy change. This implies the need for feminist movements and policymakers to remain attentive not only to overt attacks on reproductive rights but also to the more subtle discursive strategies that erode established rights and obstruct progressive reform.

2.4.4. Labour market, Migration, and Care⁶

Feminist mobilizations have long been intertwined with the evolution of capitalism, connecting cultural and socio-economic dimensions of social change. Historically, feminist struggles have critically engaged with the organization of labour, care and reproduction. Contemporary feminist activism builds on these historical legacies, expanding its focus to the labour market through innovative frames that highlight the centrality of social reproduction and the role of care in neoliberal economies (della Porta & Bonu Rosenkranz, 2025, p. 8).

Feminist activism in the labour market has focused on challenging systemic inequalities embedded in employment structures, wage hierarchies, precarious working conditions, and the persistent undervaluation of feminized work, bridging the historical legacy of the labour movement with contemporary gendered struggles. The labour market domain gained significant prominence with the rise of the international feminist strike, which sparked mass mobilizations in countries including Argentina, the United States, Spain, Switzerland, Iceland (Artus, 2024), Italy, and Poland. Originating in Latin America around 2015 with the “Ni una menos” movement protesting femicide and gender-based

⁶ This section is based on the work conducted within the thematic group on labour, migration, and care, drawing in particular on material from the draft paper *Revaluing Feminized Labour: Feminist Mobilizations and Policy Change in Contemporary Denmark and Spain* by Elin Peterson and Lise Rolandsen Agustín. It also incorporates material from the WP1 and WP2 field-work reports, particularly the DNA data prepared by Özlem Altan Olcay.

violence, the feminist strike evolved into a powerful tool for politicizing violence against women by linking it to the dynamics of contemporary capitalist accumulation (Gago, 2018). It has drawn attention to often-invisible labour trajectories, extending beyond paid employment to encompass unpaid care work and the gendered division of labour, situating these within the broader crises of social reproduction and extractivism (Gago, 2018). Moreover, the issue remains significant in contexts where social movements intersect closely with state institutions, as seen in Denmark, where trade unions have played a crucial role as allies of the feminist movement, contributing actively to advancing gender equality within the labour market (della Porta & Bonu Rosenkranz, 2025).

Our results from DNA confirm the presence of the debates related to the labour market within the feminist movements. Within the codebook that was devised, the broader categories pertaining to labour market issues included the following concepts women's rights in the labour market; LGBTIQ+ rights in the labour market; and valuing care work. More specific concepts that reflect concrete policy areas about the labour market were the following: positive discrimination in the labour market; public care facilities; wages for housework; maternity leave; parental leave; menstrual leave; and sex work. In some cases, certain country-specific codes were applied to capture national particularities. The results of the coding reveal that labour market discussions are represented through both broader rights-based discussions as well as specific policy discussions. However, their intensity shows stark variation, and not all countries have similar prioritization of labour market related issues.

Notably, Denmark and Spain emerged as cases where debates on the labour market occupy significant positions in newspaper reports. In Denmark, the top three debated topics were parental leave, women's rights in the labour market, and positive discrimination in the labour market. Further down the list of the top twenty debates, discussions around transparency in gender pay gaps also appear prominently. While there is a broad consensus in Denmark acknowledging persistent gender inequality in the labour market, there is considerably less agreement regarding the appropriate policy measures to address these issues, particularly in relation to parental leave and positive discrimination. From a policy perspective, this reveals a complex landscape in which, despite shared recognition of the problem, actors, especially from right-wing parties, often oppose demands for parental leave and positive discrimination to achieve this. This tension presents both challenges and opportunities, highlighting the need for sustained dialogue and advocacy to bridge the gap between the goal of gender equality in the labour market and the practical mechanisms required to achieve it.

Figure 10. *Top 20 debated concepts, Danish case*

In Spain, while debates concerning gender-based violence and LGBTIQ+ rights dominate the discourse, labour market issues also feature, potentially reflecting the feminist movement's growing emphasis on

care work in recent years. This suggests an emerging potential for progressive movements to influence public policy agendas in the domain of labour market reforms. Furthermore, longitudinal analysis would be valuable to assess how debates on labour market issues evolve over time, and whether their prominence within the national discourse increases in terms of both magnitude and policy relevance.

Figure 11. *Top 20 debated concepts, Spanish case*

To explore this trend in greater depth, our qualitative analysis focuses specifically on Denmark and Spain. The qualitative findings reveal that these two countries, with their distinct welfare regimes and feminist mobilization strategies, have shared concerns, but divergent trajectories in framing care-related labour as a policy issue within the broader framework of labour market policies. Having reached this conclusion drawing on data from interviews conducted with feminist activists and political stakeholders supportive of feminist agendas, as well as CFA of feminist activist documents from both countries, in the rest of this section we examine feminist mobilizations centred on female-dominated labour and feminist demands for revaluing “women’s work”.

The selection of Denmark and Spain allows for a comparison of two distinct welfare state models: Denmark’s universalist model is currently undergoing transition, while Spain’s familialist model is shifting toward increased externalisation and reliance on migrant care work. The cases are explored through an analysis of two social movement campaigns. In Denmark, the campaign revolves around the struggle for equal pay and the recognition of female-dominated professions within the welfare state. Equal pay has emerged as a central concern within the gender equality agenda, and healthcare professionals have mobilized to demand equal pay between male-dominated and female-dominated professions in the public sector, highlighting structural inequalities. In Spain, the campaign was a part of the fight for improved rights and working conditions for domestic care workers operating at the margins of the welfare state system. Organizations of domestic workers have mobilized to dignify household and care work, framing their claims within a broader feminist agenda. These efforts are closely aligned with the central messages of the March 8th (8M) mobilizations, which call for a fundamental reorganization of care in society. Thus, the Danish campaign centred on healthcare workers who represent a relatively recognized and professionalized occupational group, whereas the Spanish campaign focused on domestic workers, a marginalized collective with migrant background and limited professional recognition. These cases capture how national feminist movements, shaped by different institutional contexts and welfare legacies, have mobilized around care-related issues increasingly prominent on political agendas, particularly in the wake of global feminist waves and crises such as austerity, the COVID-19 pandemic, and #MeToo.

In the sections that follow, we begin our analysis with the problem stream, examining how feminist actors have identified and framed key labour market disputes, and highlighting the triggering events that elevated these issues to the level of public and policy concern. In the policy stream, we explore the extent to which feminist mobilizations and advocacy efforts have shaped policy agendas and contributed to political or legal reforms. Finally, in the politics stream, we analyse the broader political environment, focusing on the institutional support or resistance that shaped the outcomes of policy proposals.

Problem stream

CFA of the two campaigns reveals that “women’s work” functions as an empty signifier within contemporary feminist mobilizations. This means that it does not have a fixed meaning but instead comes to represent a chain of different demands, acquiring different meanings across discursive and national contexts. In Denmark, the discourse predominantly associates women’s work with female-dominated professions, particularly within the public sector. Here, the problem is framed as the systemic undervaluation of women’s labour in these professional domains. In Spain, women’s work is closely linked to care work and its structural undervaluation. Feminist and domestic worker collectives underscore how the challenges faced by migrant women in this sector are rooted in the broader societal invisibility and devaluation of care:

“The situations experienced by domestic workers are in some way a knot in the system that says a lot about what is happening with care and the situation of women in general. Therefore, the struggle for the improvement of domestic work is a button that triggers a much bigger social questioning.” (SPAIN_FEM_SOCMOV_06)

In both countries, advocacy efforts surrounding women’s work emphasizes its societal contribution, the centrality of care as common good, and the broader value of traditionally female-dominated professions. In the Danish context, such professions are framed as indispensable to both the functioning of society and the sustainability of the welfare state:

“What is common about our professions is the wish to make a difference for other people ... The Danish welfare society, as we know it, cannot exist without us.” (DENMARK_FEM_SOCMOV_12)

While many feminist actors frame the issue of equal pay as a structural, gendered, and societal problem, other voices adopt more instrumental and rational arguments, emphasizing the shortage of nurses. From this perspective, equal pay is framed as a necessary measure to ensure effective recruitment into the public sector and to safeguard the long-term sustainability of the welfare state.

In the Spanish context, women’s work, and particularly care work, is framed as essential to the functioning of society as well. Care is framed as a collective and indispensable good. Within this discursive framing, the revaluation of care work emerges as a pressing societal concern, closely linked to welfare, sustainability, and the organization of everyday life. Consequently, women’s work is situated within broader structures of socio-economic inequality. This perspective aligns with materialist and ecofeminist approaches, which emphasize the interdependence of labour, life, sustainability, and the environment (Fraser, 2022; Pérez, 2022). At the same time, these frameworks draw attention to a fundamental contradiction: although women’s care work is essential and widely relied upon, it is frequently carried out under precarious and unequal conditions:

“We women sustain life, and we do so in an unequal way, in conditions of exploitation and precariousness.”* (SPAIN_FEM_SOCMOV_04)

Intersectional framings are evident in both cases, though with distinct emphasis. In Denmark, the focus lies primarily on the intersections of gender and class, highlighting historical processes such as the institutionalization of gendered pay hierarchies and the devaluation of women's labour within the public sector. These problem representations draw on structural explanations rooted in patriarchal and capitalist systems. In contrast, Spanish feminist discourses foreground the contemporary interplay of heteropatriarchy, capitalism, racism, and neo-colonialism in shaping the conditions of women's work, particularly in relation to care and migration. Here, the feminist domestic workers' movement adopts an explicitly intersectional approach that recognizes the diversity of women's experiences, positions, and identities. Women migrant domestic and care workers are constructed as particularly vulnerable subjects within the current care regime, facing both economic marginalization and discursive invisibility, despite their essential role in sustaining the welfare system. Furthermore, the interview data highlight key triggering events that played a role in bringing labour disputes onto the feminist agenda and shaping their political visibility. In the Spanish context, the integration of women's work into the feminist agenda has been driven by migrant domestic worker collectives and allied anti-capitalist feminist groups focused on precarity and care. The recognition of care work has served as a unifying theme, enabling migrant care workers to connect their demands with broader feminist struggles and frame them in feminist terms:

"We formed the collective Territorio Doméstico, where we started to talk about our situation, to talk about borders, most of us were without papers, or almost all of us were without papers, and doing a job that had hardly any rights. And we started to get together in the EsKalera Karakola space [a feminist social centre], which was also something very important, to meet with feminist women who also recognized care work [...] and that connection was very important for the collective [...], because we were not alone. We were talking from a feminist perspective, and, in addition, the collective started to participate on the 8th of March demonstrations from the very beginning." (Spain, interview with feminist activist, FA13)

In Spain, trade unions were long criticized for their passivity, whereas in Denmark, the equal pay mobilizations spanned both traditional unions and grassroots initiatives that emerged from within the unions. In addition, new alliances were fostered across welfare professions, building solidarity among low-paid, female-dominated professions in the public sector. While the feminist movement supported the mobilizations, primarily by highlighting structural gender inequality and the invisibility of women's labour, it engaged less directly with the specific campaigns led by nurses. Relations with trade unions were often strained; activists expressed frustration over the lack of concrete action and, in response, decided to take matters into their own hands:

"We just wanted to be able, without the lid of the trade union, to say something about equal pay and the Public Servant Reform Act in a slightly different way than what we had said before. [...] Every time I said [in the trade union] 'why don't we do it like this' or 'shouldn't we try this' or 'shouldn't we try something new', then it had to be discussed in 15 committees. So, you lose momentum. And I understand that a trade union has to be certain in what they do. But somehow you also have to be a little bit rabid if you want to set something in motion. [...] I didn't need to yell. I needed to roar. And I felt like I couldn't roar in the trade union. But when I was out there [at the demonstrations], then I could roar." (Denmark, interview with feminist activist, FA12)

Among grassroots activists, there was growing dissatisfaction with the limited potential of collective bargaining. This frustration was particularly acute given that unions representing female-dominated professions had to find ways to collaborate with other unions, which would often result in deprioritizing gendered demands.

Inspired by international feminist strikes and Latin American mobilizations, feminist strikes in Spain became pivotal mobilizing events for articulating demands related to women's work. These actions served as strategic platforms for alliance-building, linking feminist struggles with activism in housing, environmental justice, and LGBTIQ+ rights. Within this context, care work was framed through an intersectional feminist lens:

"We practice an intersectional feminism because we know that we are criss-crossed by inequalities and precariousness that place us in very different positions in the face of patriarchy, wage labour, care, consumption, the exercise of our rights, training and citizen participation, because of the different [experiences] that some of us go through according to our origin, class, age, sexual orientation, gender identity, and abilities. But the strike belongs to all of us, there is a place for each and every one of us in our feminist strike." (SPAIN_FEM_SOCMOV_03)

In the Danish case, nurses employed the traditional strike as a means of action when collective bargaining negotiations broke down. Simultaneously, grassroots-based organizations promoted an alternative form of strike, urging midwives to commit to refrain from accepting new positions, thereby leaving vacancies in the public healthcare system until demands for decent pay and improved working conditions were met. Following the initial cycle of protest, activists experienced disappointment and burnout, driven by the emotional and economic toll of the strikes and the lack of tangible results.

Policy stream

Building on the problem stream, which outlines how feminist movements frame contentious labour market issues, the interview data provide deeper insight into how mobilizations around care and women's work have influenced both the formulation of policy proposals and the shaping of the political agenda-setting in both countries. In Spain, the 8M strikes catalysed national debates on female-dominated labour, the value of care work, and the redistribution of care responsibilities, placing feminist demands at the centre of public discourse. These themes were further amplified by the 2023 feminist general strike in the Basque Country, which explicitly called for a public, feminist care system, effectively pushing these issues onto the political agenda:

"From the feminist strikes [...], I think that at a discursive level, above all, and at an awareness-raising level, there has been an achievement. Before, care was not talked about and [for] political parties and institutions it was not an issue that was on the agenda. And I believe that the issue of care has been placed on the agenda [...]. In the end, you force the institutions and those who are governing to do something." (Spain, interview with feminist activist, FA17)

Similarly, in Denmark, the mobilizations significantly influenced public discourse, with equal pay, yet particularly for nurses, becoming a central topic in political and parliamentary debates. Thus, the mobilizations contributed to heightened attention to gender equality, equal pay, and the value of healthcare work, but predominately within the gender/class intersection:

"To us this has also been very much about creating an awareness or wanting to create a discussion in society about this and make people aware of the injustice [...] because we need the population on our side. We saw that the only way to ever create change regarding this issue, that is the support of the population." (Denmark, interview with feminist activist, FA1)

Moreover, the mobilizations also influenced the debate, awareness, and priorities of trade unions. Some activists even described this shift as an "awakening," leading to a reconfiguration of the unions' self-perception.

With regard to policy change, the most significant results were observed in the Spanish case. A key policy breakthrough was the ratification of ILO Convention No. 189 and the subsequent reform of domestic work legislation. This shift was catalysed by a landmark 2022 ruling by the Court of Justice of the European Union, which recognized the exclusion of domestic workers from unemployment benefits as a form of gender-based discrimination. As a result, the Spanish Congress of Deputies ratified the ILO Convention on decent work for domestic workers, and the government adopted a Royal Decree aimed at improving their working conditions and social security coverage. Domestic worker activists have emphasized the importance of sustained advocacy, engagement with political representatives, and alliance-building within institutions as critical strategies for achieving policy influence and legal change:

“To have that facility and those allies [leftist feminist political representatives] has been a powerful weapon to be able to carry out this political advocacy, and to be able to be in meetings with all the political parties in the Congress, in the Senate. In order to have the 189 (ILO) agreement accepted for consideration, we had to hold many meetings with many representatives of the Senate and the Congress and that was fundamental.” (Spain, interview with feminist activist, FA13)

In Denmark, the mobilization for equal pay did not lead to significant policy changes or legal reforms. Activists attributed this outcome to a lack of political will among decision-makers, reluctant to intervene in wage-setting mechanisms. Such intervention would be seen as interfering with the Danish model of collective bargaining. However, feminist mobilization did contribute to a growing public and political awareness of gendered wage inequalities in the public sector. The 2023 wage compensation granted – among others, to several female-dominated professions can at least in part be seen as a response to pacify the sustained pressure and visibility generated by the mobilizations.

The differences between the two country cases can be further explained through the distinct character of the feminist movements and broader feminist agendas at play, shaped to varying degrees by international influences. In Spain, the movement is more autonomous, grassroots-driven, explicitly anti-capitalist, integrating domestic workers’ demands into a broader intersectional feminist struggle. This approach embraces diverse subjectivities and centres migrant care workers as emblematic of intersecting oppressions. In contrast, the Danish movement is more institutionalized and sectorial, with mobilizations often emerging from within or in close connection to trade unions – though sometimes in opposition to them, with women’s organizations playing a more peripheral role in the mobilization. Here, the campaign for equal pay reflected a narrower focus, primarily centred on professionalized groups such as nurses and midwives, with limited intersectional articulation beyond gender and class.

Politics stream

Global feminist mobilizations in conjunction with contextual dynamics and recent crises have generated significant political opportunities that have facilitated collective action around the recognition and valuation of women’s care work. Key among these catalysts are the 2008 financial crisis and subsequent austerity measures, the COVID-19 pandemic, the #MeToo movement, and the international impact of feminist strikes. At the national levels, these demands have translated into calls for policy reforms, a reconceptualization of care, the revaluation of feminized labour, a more equitable redistribution of care responsibilities, and recognition of care work as essential to society and the welfare state.

In Spain, feminist mobilizations gained political traction particularly in the aftermath of the 2008 financial crisis and ensuing austerity measures, which sparked widespread discontent with precarious working conditions, especially in feminized sectors. Feminist and domestic workers’ organizations effectively aligned their agendas with broader anti-austerity movements, amplifying their reach and political visibility. Policy reforms in the early 2010s marked a significant, though partial, institutional response to

these mobilizations. The eventual ratification of ILO Convention 189 in 2022, endorsed by all parliamentary groups, demonstrates broad support and the shifting political mood toward recognizing domestic work as essential labour. Moreover, recurring feminist strikes (particularly in 2018, 2019, and 2023) have maintained pressure on the political system, supported by growing public awareness and intersectional alliances around the reorganization of care. These developments reveal an expanding political opportunity structure in Spain, in which feminist actors have gained normative legitimacy and institutional access to push for systemic care reforms.

In Denmark, the political environment has shown a more ambivalent response to feminist mobilizations, despite the prominence of equal pay on the gender equality agenda. Mobilization for equal pay gained momentum in 2020, triggered by the second wave of the #MeToo movement, which broadened public discourse around sexism to include gendered wage inequality. The COVID-19 pandemic further heightened awareness of the undervaluation of feminized care professions, especially nurses, whose essential frontline role was politically praised but materially underrecognized. However, while public and media attention increased, institutional responses remained limited. A citizens' initiative advocating for the repeal of the gender-discriminatory 1969 Public Servant Reform Act, identified as a structural source of wage inequality, was debated in Parliament, but ultimately rejected. The vote revealed a political divide: only smaller or left-wing parties supported the proposal, while the major centrist and right-leaning parties voted against it. This outcome illustrates both the increased salience of gendered labour issues in the political sphere and the persistence of institutional resistance across the political spectrum to structural change. Yet, policy developments such as the 2023 wage increases for several female-dominated professions suggest that public pressure and union mobilization have begun to influence incremental policy adjustments.

Main Takeaways

In recent years, feminist mobilizations in Spain and Denmark have succeeded in reframing care and women's work as central public and political concerns. In both countries, mobilizations around women's care work use strategic framings that invoke the notion of the "common good", aligning feminist demands with broader values such as welfare sustainability, equality, and social justice. These demands extend beyond wages and labour rights, articulating broader visions of the kind of society worth defending. However, the scope and framing of these mobilizations diverge. Danish activism tends to focus more narrowly on welfare and structural gender inequality, linking it to class-based struggles. In contrast, Spanish mobilizations adopt a broader intersectional framework, addressing the interlocking systems of heteropatriarchy, capitalism, racism, and colonialism, and situating care within a wider discourse on the sustainability of life. In both contexts, structural framings gained traction, enabled by favourable political opportunity structures shaped by global movements such as #MeToo and the COVID-19 crisis.

Our analysis shows that feminist actors have had a strong influence on the problem stream, effectively constructing "women's work" as a structural and intersectional issue. In Spain, feminist actors and as policy entrepreneurs, including activists, collectives, and institutional allies, translated these framings into policy influence, resulting in concrete legal reforms such as the ratification of ILO Convention 189 and improvements in domestic work legislation. Stronger alignment between movement demands and political institutions facilitated significant legal reforms in the domain of domestic work. In contrast, Denmark's policy stream remained constrained, with limited institutional responsiveness and reliance on collective bargaining structures that restrict state intervention.

In the political stream, feminist actors in both countries capitalized on crisis-driven windows of opportunity, both nationally and globally. However, while Spain's political context allowed for broader institutional engagement and cross-party support, Denmark exhibited more resistance, with key reform proposals blocked by centrist and right-wing parties. Across both contexts, strategic framing and coalition-building proved crucial for gaining traction, yet tensions emerged between radical demands and institutional constraints. While both movements invoked structural critiques and were shaped by transnational momentum, such as #MeToo and the COVID-19 crisis, their strategic orientations, alliance-building efforts, inclusivity of subject positions, and feminist advocacy varied significantly, influencing their capacity to challenge dominant institutional frameworks and achieve transformative change. These dynamics reveal the importance of timing, discourse, and alliances in shaping policy outcomes, and highlight how feminist strategies are both enabled and limited by their embeddedness in national political and institutional configurations.

2.4.5. Intersectionality⁷

Contemporary feminist movements are increasingly characterized by the incorporation of intersectional perspectives, recognizing the co-constitutive nature of overlapping systems of inequality, such as gender, race, ethnicity, class, and sexuality. Intersectionality has gained significant momentum in the context of recent global feminist mobilizations (della Porta & Bonu Rosenkranz, 2025), which have increasingly addressed broader struggles against multiple, intersecting forms of oppression. For social movements, intersectionality functions not only as an analytical frame that critiques patriarchy, but also as a lens through which racism, capitalism, and neoliberalism are understood as deeply interconnected systems (Evans & Lépinard, 2019). Moreover, intersectionality serves as a tool for shaping collective identities, influencing organizational structures and strategies, and facilitating coalition-building both within and across social movements (Ayoub, 2019; Ciccio & Roggeband, 2021).

While feminist movements have largely embraced intersectional framings and practices, the integration of intersectionality into public policy remains slow and uneven (Garcia & Zajicek, 2022; Manuel, 2007). Intersectionality-based policy analyses often focus on the design and outcomes of public policies but frequently assume that intersectional concerns are already present on the policy agenda. However, the processes that determine whether and how these concerns are recognized and framed as policy problems remain underexplored.

To explore when, how, and why intersectionality enters, or fails to enter, the policymaking processes, our analysis in this thematic section focuses on four countries: Italy, Spain, Denmark, and Slovenia. This analysis seeks to show that the incorporation of intersectional perspectives in public policy is not only a matter of normative commitment or institutional openness. Rather, it is shaped by the interplay of discursive, political, and institutional dynamics - including the strategies, alliances, and agenda-setting efforts of feminist activists, policy entrepreneurs, and political actors - which vary across contexts and policy domains. To explore these dynamics, the analysis draws on empirical data from interviews with

⁷ This section is based on the work conducted within the thematic group on intersectionality, drawing in particular on material from the draft paper *The Bumpy Path of the Intersectional Perspective in Public Policy: A Comparative Analysis through Multiple Streams Framework* by Giada Bonu Rosenkranz, Rok Smrdelj, Lise Rolandsen Agustín and Ines Campillo Poza.

In this section, we draw on empirical material from interviews and CFA, where intersectionality emerged as a cross-cutting perspective across the country cases. In the DNA, there was no predefined set of concepts explicitly categorized under the theme of intersectionality. However, the broader list of concepts encompassed issues that intersect with multiple axes of inequality, reflecting experiences of women, sexual minorities, migrants, and children.

feminist activists and political stakeholders who support feminist agendas, as well as on CFA of feminist activist documents and parliamentary debates in the four countries.

The four selected cases were brought together because they display diversity along several key dimensions: the extent to which gender equality has been institutionalized; the historical patterns and intensity of feminist mobilization; the role and scope of state involvement in the provision of social welfare; and the degree of influence exercised by conservative and anti-gender actors. This diversity is essential for capturing the wide variety of debates on intersectionality across Europe. These trajectories help explain variations in how intersectionality is addressed in policy, but they do not fully capture the political dynamics, particularly when grassroots movements, informal networks, and transnational alliances are taken into account. Policy frameworks tend to be more structured and comparable, whereas politics on the ground often unfolds in more fluid, cross-cutting, and sometimes contradictory ways that defy neat categorization - a reminder of the limitations of typological thinking in this field.

Within this broader view, Italy is marked by weak equality institutions and limited institutional space for structural change; Denmark sustains strong social protections but often resists targeted or differentiated policy approaches; Slovenia combines formal equality institutions receptive to feminist input with technocratic constraints that can limit transformative change; and Spain has comparatively extensive integration of intersectionality into public policy, albeit now facing political backlash and internal resistance. The cases also show different feminist mobilization logics (strong street-based activism in Spain, expert-driven approaches in Denmark, legalist strategies in Slovenia, and resistant mobilization in Italy) as well as different forms of anti-gender backlash (institutionalized opposition in Italy, cultural pushback in Denmark, religiously framed resistance in Slovenia, and highly contested landscape in Spain). In terms of mobilization and policy influence, each of the selected countries contributes with a distinct analytical lens: the Italian case allows us to examine the friction between legal contestation and intersectional claims in a hostile political environment with feminist intersectional resistance; Denmark reveals the limits of intersectional mainstreaming even within supposedly advanced equality regimes; Slovenia illustrates the paradox of progressive legalism under threat; and the Spanish case shows strong bottom-up mobilization, intersectional policy framings and a contested welfare structure.

For each country, we identified the most salient gender debates during the period from 2010 to 2023. In Italy, the key issues were GBV and education. In Denmark, debates focused on GBV and equal pay. In Slovenia, marriage equality and reproductive rights emerged as the most significant topics. In Spain, GBV and care work were the central themes shaping public discourse and policy discussions.

These contextual differences across the selected country cases allow for a comparative analysis of how intersectionality is being realized across contexts, and whether it encounters similar or distinct obstacles. While the policy debates vary, the strength of this comparative design lies in its comprehensive empirical approach, enabling us to identify recurring dynamics and diverse barriers to the inclusion of intersectionality in public policymaking across a variety of policy fields.

In the following sections, we begin by analysing the problem stream, focusing on how public policies on gender-related issues do - or do not - address intersecting inequalities. In the policy stream, we examine which intersectional claims succeed or fail to enter the policy agenda. As the in/exclusion of intersectionality in policy-making processes is shaped by the interplay of discursive, political, and institutional dynamics, the politics stream pays particular attention to the broader political environment within each country case, enabling or constraining the integration of intersectionality in public policy.

Problem stream

The findings indicate that the country cases are marked by a limited and often superficial engagement with intersectionality in political discourse. While there is a general rhetorical commitment to developing intersectional approaches in policymaking, this rarely translates into substantive agenda-setting. Feminist policymakers may demonstrate awareness of intersectionality, yet this awareness does not carry over into parliamentary debates, where silence around intersectionality is pronounced, both in how problems are defined and in the solutions proposed.

“As for intersectional inequalities, I would stress that we have a particularly high risk of poverty among women, especially older women, and much more needs to be done in this area. In addition, more attention should be paid to the situation of migrant women, refugees, Roma women and other vulnerable groups of women. When you look at the data on women and men with foreign citizenship, you see huge differences in employment – not only between the general population and immigrants, but also between men and women within the immigrant population.”
(Slovenia, interview with feminist political stakeholder, FPS4)

A significant disjuncture emerges between the discourse of feminist movements - where intersectionality frequently plays a central role - and institutional political discourse, where it remains marginal, sporadic, or entirely absent. Activist framings of intersectionality seldom permeate mainstream political discourses, resulting in a persistent gap between movement-based conceptualizations and institutional uptake. This disconnect constitutes a major obstacle to the integration of intersectionality into policy agendas.

It is further reflected in the contrast between the mutually constitutive understandings of intersectionality advanced by feminist movements and the additive approaches often employed in political discourse. Among the cases analysed, Spain stands out as a notable exception. Here, intersectional framings - particularly those linking gender, class, and migration - have gained traction in agenda-setting and problem articulation, especially in relation to care and domestic work, precarious labour conditions, and gender-based violence. Spain thus illustrates the potential for intersectionality to shape the problem stream of policymaking when supported by strong bottom-up mobilization and favourable discursive and political conditions.

Policy stream

Intersectionality remains largely absent from policy formulation and institutional frameworks for policy design and implementation. This absence can be attributed to limitations within political institutional design, which are typically organized along siloed lines, addressing inequality categories separately and by distinct ministries or departments, with minimal horizontal coordination. This fragmented institutional architecture hinders the development of intersectional policy tools and solutions. For example, in Slovenia, the political system operates in a compartmentalized manner, lacking systematic dialogue and coordination between directorates and departments:

“At the Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities, I also covered the Sector for Equal Opportunities, which directly deals with gender equality. In my opinion, this sector was not sufficiently integrated into the work of other directorates but was treated as a separate unit. There was no major cooperation, for example with the Directorate for Social Affairs, the Directorate for the Disabled, or with the labour market.” (Slovenia, interview with feminist political stakeholder, FPS6)

At the same time, the institutional infrastructure for gender equality remains weak, resulting in a limited internal demand for the integration of intersectionality into policy frameworks and structures. Involve-

ment of civil society in policy-making processes is limited and there is a general lack of awareness regarding the relevance and importance of intersectional approaches. As a result, the advanced intersectional knowledge and nuanced demands articulated by feminist movements struggle to find entry points into institutional politics. Moreover, legal approaches tend to dominate over considerations of social complexity. Policymaking often prioritizes alignment with established legal categories - typically treating inequalities as separate and discrete - rather than embracing intersectional perspectives that reflect the lived realities of diverse groups. Spain, once again, emerges as the exception. In this case, the policy stream converges with the problem stream through the explicit articulation of intersectionality as a guiding principle in policy solutions and design. Policy influence of feminist movements is amplified through processes of party “movementization”, enabling a more direct translation of intersectional demands into institutional agendas. This is exemplified by the *Third Strategic Plan for Effective Equality of Women and Men 2022–2025* published by Instituto de las Mujeres, an autonomous agency under the Spanish Ministry of Equality. This policy paper explicitly establishes intersectionality as one of its guiding principles: *“In this approach, women’s lives cannot be explained by a single explanatory factor, such as gender, but by its interrelation with others, such as racialization, social class, origin, disability, etc. How all of these factors work together and influence each other, depending on the situated context in which women’s lives unfold, ultimately explains how inequality is experienced and manifested in their lives.”* (Instituto de las Mujeres, 2022, p. 13)

Politics stream

There is a notable absence of explicit political support for intersectionality, and the broader political climate is marked by polarization and institutional resistance. This resistance manifests not only in general reluctance to advance gender equality policies but also in the unwillingness to challenge entrenched institutional structures, particularly the siloed organization of inequalities in policymaking and the lack of horizontal coordination across ministries and departments. These structural and political barriers significantly constrain the development of intersectional approaches. In Italy, this institutional backlash is evident. A striking example is the withdrawal of the *Educating for Diversity in School* pamphlets, which illustrates the extent to which intersectional and inclusive educational initiatives can be undermined:

“The minute the Catholic Church raised its voice, MIUR [Ministry of Education] retreated. There was no institutional courage to defend those materials.” (Italy, interview with feminist political stakeholder, FPS)

Political fragmentation and the lack of integrated welfare pose significant constraints on the development of intersectional policies. In this context, far-right actors, conservative bureaucracies, and religious institutions function as powerful gatekeepers, obstructing progressive policy initiatives. While policy entrepreneurs, like feminist civil society organizations and movements, can serve as critical enablers of intersectional policymaking, their efforts are frequently undermined by limited political receptivity and marked reluctance by policymakers to incorporate these perspectives into formal policy agendas and policy design. In Denmark, for instance, feminist activists have challenged the absence of intersectional thinking within the political and legal systems. Their critiques highlight how institutional barriers not only hinder policy change but also shape the strategies of the movements themselves. In response, activists increasingly engage in intersectional alliance-building, forging coalitions across different axes of inequality to amplify their influence and navigate institutional constraints:

“Our entire legislation [...] is tailored in a way that addresses each discrimination ground separately. [...] Well, we would like to look into that. When we work in this way, with separate grounds instead of considering them together, are we missing something? And we have been looking into

that, and we started reaching out to different other organizations, across... that could be LGBT+ Denmark, Sabaah, and also Danish Institute for Human Rights, for instance, and others, which might be able to document, also in terms of cases, [...] with stories about what this actually means.” (Denmark, interview with feminist activist, FA11)

In the Italian context, feminist movements have historically maintained a critical stance vis-à-vis state institutions, which has limited their direct influence on policy-making processes. Although intersectionality features prominently within feminist discourse and activism, this institutional distance has impeded the translation of intersectional perspectives into formal policy frameworks.

Main Takeaways

Across the four country cases, the analytical findings in problem stream reveal a general awareness of intersectionality among policymakers and the articulation of intersectional demands by feminist movements. While intersectionality is central to activist narratives, especially in articulating the lived experiences of multiply marginalized groups, most political actors adopt additive rather than mutually constitutive approaches to inequality, limiting the transformative potential of intersectionality. Spain stands out as an exception, where strong bottom-up mobilization and favourable political conditions have enabled intersectional frames, particularly around gender, class, and migration, to shape public problem definitions, especially in areas such as care work and gender-based violence.

The political and institutional conditions necessary for intersectionality to gain traction in policy formulation, design, and implementation are lacking in Italy, Denmark, and Slovenia. The institutionalization of intersectionality in policymaking breaks down in the transition from problems to solutions, from (partial) awareness to concrete policies, and from feminist movements to political institutions. Spain again offers a notable contrast: its strategic gender equality plan explicitly incorporates intersectionality as a guiding principle, facilitated by the presence of feminist actors within state structures and ongoing processes of party movementization.

A lack of explicit political support for intersectionality and widespread institutional resistance shape an unfavourable political climate across most countries. Entrenched policymaking structures, political polarization, and the influence of conservative actors, such as religious institutions and far-right parties, act as significant barriers. Even where civil society organizations act as policy entrepreneurs, their capacity to influence institutional agendas remains limited. Overall, while the political stream is constrained, emerging practices of coalition-building suggest new openings for intersectional advocacy.

The problem, policy, and politics streams should align for a window of opportunity to open; the findings show that this does not happen in the cases of Italy, Denmark and Slovenia. Obstacles are found in relation to each of the streams and strong intersectional public policies are not developed. However, in the Spanish case the three streams do align, and intersectional policies are developed although obstacles are encountered in the implementation phase.

The question is how to strengthen the connection between intersectional awareness, feminist mobilization, and effective policy design. The analysis underscores that the successful integration of intersectionality requires: 1) a clear and resonant framing of the problem; 2) the presence of policy entrepreneurs capable of translating intersectional claims into actionable policy proposals; 3) a political arena in which civil society actors and social movements can frame intersectional concerns in ways that resonate within policy-making spaces; and 4) institutional structures that enable effective coordination across inequality policies. Even in contexts with strong equality frameworks, intersectionality does not automatically enter the policy agenda. Instead, it requires strategic framing, cross-sectoral alliances, and favourable political opportunity structures.

2.5. Discussion

This report strived to demonstrate the analytical and explanatory power of integrating the Multiple Streams Framework (MSF) with framing theory to understand the dynamics of gender-related agenda-setting and policymaking across diverse European contexts. The MSF provides the conceptual grounding for examining the conditions under which policy entrepreneurs succeed in coupling the problem, policy, and politics streams across various social topics, thereby advancing issues to decision-making processes. Framing theory complements this by unpacking the construction of meaning by the actors involved – i.e. the ways in which feminist and anti-gender actors and coalitions define problems and promote particular solutions in ways that resonate with broader cultural and institutional logics. This combined analytical lens has enabled us to observe how actors operate within and against institutional constraints, strategically shaping the definition of issues and solutions to influence policymaking.

Our multi-method design - combining Critical Frame Analysis (CFA), Discourse Network Analysis (DNA), and semi-structured interviews - was crucial for operationalizing the theoretical integration. CFA allowed us to map the content, structure, and resonance of frames as they concretely appear in documents, and advocacy materials, capturing how issues are articulated and connected to normative frameworks. DNA, in turn, provided quantified data on which discussions and actors captured the public realm across the cases, while also offering potential for deeper analysis into the architecture of discursive coalitions and confrontations evolving over time within specific country cases. Interviews provided in-depth insights into actor strategies, their perceptions of political opportunity, and the constraints they face in translating mobilization into policy agenda.

The combination of these approaches and methods made it possible to address the complexity of agenda-setting and policymaking across the five thematic areas: LGBTIQ+ rights; gender-based violence; health and reproductive rights; labour market, migration and care; and intersectionality. It also enabled us to account for national variations, while drawing out cross-country patterns that speak to the research questions (see above p. 11).

Across the problem stream, we observed that feminist actors often reframe established issues in ways that heighten their urgency, sometimes linking them to broader human rights or democratic principles to broaden appeal. For example, reproductive rights in Slovenia were framed as integral to democratic legacy, enabling actors to resist policy rollbacks even in politically restrictive moments. Analysing the policy stream, we found that coalitions frequently drew on international norms, EU directives, or evidence-based models to propose viable solutions, demonstrating how transnational policy flows can be strategically localized. The politics stream revealed the significance of party configurations, electoral cycles, alliances, and shifting public opinion - factors that could either constrain or amplify feminist agendas.

The DNA findings added an important layer to this picture by visualizing the positioning and connectivity of actors across debates. Feminist and anti-gender actors tend to form distinct, internally cohesive clusters, yet engaging in overlapping discursive arenas where their frames come into tension and compete for dominance. These confrontations were not merely rhetorical but shaped the viability of policy proposals by influencing public discourse and political receptivity.

A consistent finding is that feminist and anti-gender actors are engaged in ongoing, mutually shaping contention. Anti-gender mobilizations often seek to reframe feminist gains as threats to tradition, family, or national identity, deploying emotionally charged narratives and strategic ambiguities to mobilize resistance. Feminist actors, in response, not only counter-frame but also develop hybrid strategies -

sometimes emphasizing rights-based clarity in their communication, at other times also adopting strategic ambiguity to reach broader audiences.

The comparative perspective has highlighted that feminist actors can be successful in shifting agendas even in challenging contexts. In Spain, sustained mobilization against violence against women successfully aligned with political shifts to produce landmark legislation. In Slovenia, feminist actors leveraged democratic frames to defend reproductive rights from erosion. In Italy, despite an often-hostile political climate, targeted alliances with sympathetic policymakers facilitated incremental gains in gender equality measures. In France, feminist movements were able to exploit the political window of opportunity that allowed legislative progress on health and reproductive rights, as well as to integrate intersectional practices within the repertoire of action of feminism. In Denmark, feminist actors framed labour market equality and care provision in terms of economic competitiveness and productivity, which resonated with political priorities and enabled policy uptake, even if migration-related gender issues were silenced or left unaddressed. In Turkey, feminist mobilizations kept gender-based violence visible in public discourse, despite shrinking civic space, using international frameworks and intersectional alliances to sustain pressure on policymakers. In Poland, mass protests against abortion restrictions, combined with transnational advocacy, not only contested regressive measures, but also kept reproductive rights at the centre of the political agenda. In Greece, feminist interventions around GBV legislation took advantage of international commitments, including the Istanbul Convention, to push through reforms despite anti-gender narratives framing such policies as externally imposed. Taken together, these cases demonstrate that success is rarely the result of structural openings alone; rather, it emerges from the capacity to recognize, create, and exploit moments of opportunity - often in the face of organised and well-resourced opposition.

Importantly, our findings complicate the notion of backsliding. While policy reversals and anti-gender mobilisations remain persistent and consequential, the trajectory of gender equality policy is neither linear nor predetermined. Recent developments illustrate this complexity: Denmark, Slovenia, and Spain have adopted legal reforms redefining sexual violence and rape on the basis of affirmative consent through “Only Yes Means Yes” provisions; France has enshrined abortion rights in its constitution; and in Italy, new legislation has introduced femicide as a distinct category in criminal law. These policy achievements testify to the tangible outcomes of sustained civil society mobilisation. Across our cases, feminist interventions - whether through rapid mobilisation, strategic framing, or coalition-building - have demonstrated the capacity to halt, slow, or even reverse regressive trends. Backsliding, therefore, should not be understood as a one-way erosion of rights, but rather as a dynamic and contested political space in which feminist and anti-gender actors actively shape, challenge, and reconfigure the direction and substance of policy over time. Recognising this ongoing contestation is essential for understanding that moments of regression can also generate counter-mobilisations, opening new opportunities for feminist intervention and policy innovation, which would be significantly strengthened and sustained through political, institutional, and economic support.

Relatedly, one of the central insights from this research is that windows of opportunity are not only structural openings created by exogenous events or shifts in the political landscape; they can also be actively produced by feminist actors themselves. By reframing problems to fit dominant policy narratives, forging cross-sector alliances, and exploiting ambiguities in political discourse, these actors create the conditions for agenda and policymaking access. This is particularly significant in hostile or indifferent political climates, where such windows are unlikely to emerge without deliberate action.

Our findings also confirm that clarity as well as ambiguity have strategic value in both feminist and anti-gender mobilizations. Explicit framing helps to crystallize issues, rally supporters, and pressure decision-

makers. Ambiguity, however, can function as a bridging device, allowing coalitions to accommodate diverse constituencies and avoid alienating potential allies in polarized contexts. The interplay between these two modes of framing is a recurrent feature across our cases and thematic areas.

Overall, the analysis addressed three overarching lines of inquiry. First, we examined the factors that influence the *inclusion or exclusion* of gender-related issues on political agendas. The evidence demonstrates that inclusion depends on the alignment of the problem, policy, and politics streams, mediated by the capacity of feminist actors to deploy resonant frames and to navigate or reshape opportunity structures. Exclusion, in turn, often results from hostile political configurations, dominant counter-frames, and the inability to align streams within available timeframes. Second, we explored how feminist mobilisations contribute to *policy impact* across different contexts. The findings show that feminist actors influence agendas not merely by responding to openings but by actively creating them - through reframing, coalition-building, and strategic engagement with political and policy elites. Third, we considered the insights gained from a *comparative approach*. The cross-country analysis reveals that, while contexts differ in political opportunity structures, legal frameworks, and cultural narratives, the combination of structural positioning, discursive and action strategy tend to shape opportunities for change. This pattern is visible across all five thematic areas, indicating a degree of transferability in both challenges faced and tactics employed.

In sum, the integration of MSF and framing theory, supported by a multi-method empirical approach, has provided a nuanced account of gender-related agenda-setting and policymaking in Europe. The findings emphasise the necessity of analysing both the structural and the discursive dimensions of policy processes, and they affirm the agency of feminist actors in shaping political agendas - even in times of backsliding and intensified opposition.

2.6. Conclusion

This report has delivered on the promise set out in the project application to conduct a multidimensional and multi-level cross-country comparative analysis of key thematic areas in gender equality policymaking. Building on the mapping of salient issues and debates across eight country cases, we identified five thematic areas - LGBTIQ+ rights; gender-based violence; health and reproductive rights; labour market, migration and care; and intersectionality - that have been at the centre of both feminist mobilization and anti-gender contestation. Through in-depth analysis of the policy processes in each thematic area, we have explained how specific gendered and feminist frames reached the political agenda and, in some cases, succeeded in producing policy change. Conversely, we have identified conditions under which these frames were excluded, or remained unaddressed, thereby failing to translate into policy outcomes. Across the cases, the trajectories and outcomes of feminist frames were shaped by the interaction between problem recognition, policy feasibility, and political receptivity, as well as by the strategic agency of feminist actors in framing issues, mobilising allies, dealing with internal conflicts, and navigating institutional arenas.

The analysis confirmed that feminist and anti-gender actors deploy different repertoires, often rooted in competing values, norms, and visions of society. Feminist movements used both explicit rights-based frames and strategic ambiguity to broaden support, while anti-gender actors combined familiar references to tradition, religion, and national identity with adaptive discursive strategies that repackage these ideas in contemporary terms, enabling them to contest reforms, resist change, and, in some cases, roll back existing policies. These interactions were not static but evolved in response to shifting political contexts, electoral cycles, and international developments.

By tracing these dynamics across local, national, regional, and transnational levels, we have shown how alliances - both supportive and antagonistic - shape the opportunities for inclusion in institutional policymaking. Patterns of coalition-building, whether between feminist movements and political parties, or between anti-gender actors and religious institutions, have had a decisive influence on whether gender equality issues advanced or stalled. In some cases, such as Spain's GBV reforms or Slovenia's defence of reproductive rights, feminist actors successfully forged cross-level alliances that reinforced their claims. In other cases, anti-gender coalitions drew on transnational networks to block or reverse policy change, as seen in certain LGBTIQ+ rights and reproductive health debates.

The cross-country comparative approach has revealed not only national differences in political opportunity structures and cultural framing but also shared patterns that transcend borders. In all contexts, the articulation of frames and the use of multi-level alliances emerged as critical determinants of agenda-setting success and policy impact. The comparative perspective has also clarified that windows of opportunity are not merely structural openings but can be actively constructed by feminist actors through reframing, exploiting contradictions and lack of consistency in opponents' positions, and mobilizing international norms to pressure policymakers.

Finally, by addressing intersectionality, the analysis has revealed the importance of recognising multiple and overlapping axes of inequality in shaping inclusion and exclusion in policy processes. Intersectional frames - where they were present - enabled feminist actors to broaden coalitions and address the lived realities of diverse constituencies. At the same time, these frames sometimes faced political resistance or strategic sidelining, highlighting the ongoing challenge of embedding intersectionality into the entire policy process, including policy outputs and outcomes.

In sum, the findings of this task advance our understanding of when, how, and why feminist and anti-gender movements draw on frames, actors, and alliances across levels to influence policy agendas, and when they choose - or are forced - to refrain from doing so. They foreground the agency of feminist actors in shaping political possibilities even in adverse contexts, the adaptability of anti-gender mobilizations, and the contested nature of gender equality policymaking in contemporary Europe.

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